

D6.8

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED

Exploitation and Sustainability Plan - updated

WHITE

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SUSTCERT4BIOBASED methodology (GA No. 101059785) for the project's exploitation and sustainability plan builds on existing expertise, tools and templates developed internally by White Research while also taking into account European Commission guidelines and best practices available in literature. Part of the standard methodology adopted has already been developed in previous research projects where White Research was a beneficiary, such as the INCISIVE (GA. 952179) project. This approach ensures optimal resource allocation and adherence to project requirements. Ad hoc and tailored modifications were integrated to the methodology used by SUSTCERT4BIOBASED to comply with GA conditions, EU recommendations and project specificities. This report presents the adjusted methodology as it was further developed and applied within SUSTCERT4BIOBASED.

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ABBREVIATIONS

BG	Background IP
BMT	BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool
CA	Consortium Agreement
CBA	Cost benefit analysis
CC	Creative Commons
CSLs	Certifications schemes and labels
D&E	Dissemination and Exploitation
EC	European Commission
EPO	European Patent Office
ER	Exploitable Result
GA	Grant Agreement
HE	Horizon Europe
HRP	Horizon Results Platform
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KER	Key Exploitable Result
NDA	Non-Disclosure Agreement
ROL	Results Ownership List
SMEs	Small and medium-sized enterprises
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

For research projects to create lasting impact, it's essential to go beyond just producing results—those results need to be protected, shared, and effectively used. The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project has developed a structured IPR and exploitation strategy to ensure that its key outcomes are not only identified and safeguarded but also have a clear path for future use and sustainability.

This report outlines the project's approach to managing intellectual assets, defining ownership structures, and implementing dissemination and exploitation actions. The aim is to make sure that the knowledge and innovations generated within the project reach the right stakeholders—whether policymakers, industry players, or certification bodies in the bio-based sector. A key part of this report also highlights the collaboration with BIOBASEDCERT Cluster, where a joint exploitation strategy, strengthening synergies and knowledge transfer was also implemented.

Key Highlights of the report:

- **Chapter 1:** introduces the objectives of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Innovation Management Strategy, outlining its general ambition and obligations under Horizon Europe.
- **Chapter 2:** provides an overview of key innovation management concepts, including IP and IPR, ownership, access rights, exploitable results (KERs), joint ownership, and digital IP protection.
- **Chapter 3:** details IP protection measures, covering patents, trademarks, trade secrets, copyrights, domain names, and database rights (sui generis protection).
- **Chapter 4:** focuses on the strategy throughout the project's lifecycle, from the Grant Agreement (GA) preparation stage to the post-project phase, outlining roles, responsibilities, and available European Commission support services.
- **Chapter 5:** explains the methodology for identifying Background IP, Key Exploitable Results (KERs), and IP ownership structures, including templates used throughout the project.
- **Chapter 6:** provides an overview of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's Background IP and identified KERs, with a special emphasis on jointly owned results with HARMONITOR and STAR4BBS.
- **Chapter 7:** outlines the IPR management and exploitation plans for SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's results, including joint ownership agreements and publication strategies.
- **Chapter 8:** presents the common exploitation strategy for SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's KERs, highlighting their value proposition to key stakeholders.
- **Chapter 9:** details the individual post-project exploitation and valorization plans per partner, ensuring long-term sustainability of project outcomes.
- Conclusions

Annex 1: BIOBASEDCERT Cluster Co-ownership Agreement

1. Introduction

1.1. Objective of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Innovation Management strategy

A main objective of the project's Innovation Management strategy is to carefully monitor activities during the implementation of the project, keeping track of any knowledge or Intellectual Property (IP) brought to it by project partners as well as of results generated from the activities.

Therefore, the Innovation Strategy sets the ground for monitoring the protection of IP and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) within the consortium, which eventually will support the creation of value from the exploitation and use of the project results and facilitate further innovation from the assets developed during the project, in addition to their successful deployment.

Besides the protection of exploitable results (ERs), the objectives of the Innovation Strategy also reflect the intention to ensure and support the exploitation and sustainability of project outcomes and their wider availability to all relevant stakeholders. Importantly, when relevant for each result, exploitation of results will rely on commercial and scientific activities that will take place after the project's completion.

Following a structured strategy that relies on best practices and official EC guidelines will ensure that all the innovative ideas, methodologies, and results stemming from SUSTCERT4BIOBASED are exhaustively identified and pertinently protected, thus helping maximise their impact by being made widely available to other stakeholders through commercialisation or, when applicable, scientific or other type of use.

To this end, the specific objectives of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Innovation Management strategy are the following:

- Define the iterative approach that will yield a comprehensive identification of Background (BG) and the results that emerge from all the activities within the lifecycle of the project.
- Define the methodological framework for the management of all BG and (exploitable) results, including the definition of rights for access and reuse within the project and the potential IPR protection avenues.
- Develop a common understanding among the consortium partners concerning IP-related concepts, as well as a risk mitigation approach, in order to prevent – or, if not possible, eventually resolve – potential IP conflicts.
- Deliver an exhaustive identification of IPR management strategies for all exploitable results of the project as well as from each partner's perspective.
- Relatedly, define ownership for each exploitable result, thus also serving as guidance for partners when they draft their own joint ownership agreements by not only identifying ownership shares but also other underlying usage conditions and responsibilities.
- Help define the more detailed exploitation strategies for the project's key exploitable results (KERs) in the relevant project tasks by not only identifying the relevant types of exploitation for each KER but also discussing how the KERs cover the needs of and add value to the main relevant stakeholders.
- Define the main outcomes of interest and the overall post-project valorisation plans for each consortium partner.
- Define the roles and responsibilities of each project partner to contribute to the project's innovation management. Successfully fulfilling most of the previous objectives is contingent

upon collecting timely input provided and, where relevant, agreed upon by all relevant partners, hence the (pro)active involvement of the consortium in this task is crucial.

1.2. General aim and ambition of Innovation Management activities

In the context of international research projects, it is crucial to understand how to manage IPR as their improper handling could cause real problems concerning the validity of the rights granted, or the risks of legal disputes between partners.¹

Ensuring that IP is timely identified and that the ownership and protection of the generated IP are adequately allocated will help with the smooth reuse and exploitation of the project results. In order to record all the relevant activities linked to the conception and development of an invention, it is advisable to keep a proper track of the innovation process, providing crucial evidence regarding the date of the invention, its authorship and ownership. A timely disclosure and accurate description of the invention would also help in the choice of whether to pursue further IPR protection and what means or type of protection to use (e.g., patent, utility model, design, trade secrets). Thanks to these records, partner organisations and consortium partners will be able to monitor the creation of results with exploitable potential within the frame of the project and to have a clear understanding of the ownership of each IP asset and result, their rights to access/use them, and the pertinent ways to protect them.

Ultimately, creating value for partners, relevant stakeholders and society as a whole is the main objective of publicly-funded research and innovation projects. Innovation management efforts are essential to support project partners in boosting the value and impact generated by their efforts beyond the consortium.

Defining a tailored and appropriate innovation management strategy is also important in order to support consortium partners with the necessary balance to both comply with Open Science requirements while at the same time ensuring the protection of IP to support the commercial exploitation of the project results.

In general, IPR promote economic, social, and cultural progress by stimulating creative work and technological innovation. For small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), particularly, a proper IP strategy and protection can help enhance market growth and support competitiveness, prevent loss of market share, prevent reputational damages, and give prospective investors the incentive to finance their activities².

1.3. Obligations under Horizon Europe

A main objective of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project's Innovation Management strategy is to comply with the explicit obligations that beneficiaries of Horizon Europe (HE) programmes must fulfill. In general, these rules aim to ensure that partners in a collaborative R&I project make good use of all the knowledge, IP and results from the project to maximise its impact and added value.

The obligations discussed below may need to be fulfilled either individually or as a consortium. Building upon a clear understanding of these obligations, the present Innovation Management

¹ European IP Helpdesk (2022a).

² European IP Helpdesk & Enterprise Europe Network (2024).

strategy has been formulated in a way that will ensure that following it will provide such compliance. To this end, this section reviews EC guidelines and summarises the most relevant obligations under Horizon Europe related to Innovation Management.

HE rules establish guiding principles for Innovation Management concerning aspects such as ownership, IP protection, access rights, exploitation of project results, etc. Most of these rules are delineated in the Grant Agreement (GA) and the Consortium Agreement (CA). While the GA contains 'default' overarching rules, the CA specifies certain rules further according to what is agreed upon by the project's consortium.

Obligation to protect. A key obligation for HE beneficiaries is that the project's results must always be adequately protected if (a) they can reasonably be expected to be commercially exploited and (b) protecting them is possible, reasonable and justified. Such 'adequate' protection of results implies that protection shall be attained for an appropriate period of time and with an appropriate territorial coverage.

Innovation management activities must therefore ensure that exploitable results (ERs) will be captured, assessed and appropriately protected, in order to support their commercial exploitation. This includes the obligation to define concrete measures for Key Exploitable Results (KERs)¹.

Mandatory Results Ownership List (ROL). Under Horizon Europe, beneficiaries must include a list of KERs in their final reporting, where the following information pertaining to each KER must be present²: (i) description, (ii) ownership status, (iii) sector of application, and (iv) protection measures - geographical coverage (if applicable). As a minimum, the ownership status information must include whether the ownership is single or joint, the name of the owner(s), the country of establishment of the owner(s) and whether the results will be exploited by the owner(s)³. Failure to present this ROL will block both the submission of the final periodic report and the final payment.

Obligation to exploit. Another crucial obligation is the responsibility of beneficiaries to do their best to exploit the project's KERs they own: consortium partners must, up to four years after the end of the project, take measures to exploit results their results either directly or indirectly⁴. In particular, indirect exploitation refers to the exploitation by another legal entity through the transfer or licensing of the IPR pertaining to the KER.

A subsequent obligation is formalised in HE' Model GA as follows: "If, despite a beneficiary's best efforts, the results are not exploited within one year after the end of the action, the beneficiaries must (unless otherwise agreed in writing with the granting authority) use the Horizon Results Platform (HRP) to find interested parties to exploit the results."⁵ The HRP can also provide a commonly used platform to help making results visible⁶.

¹ European IP Helpdesk (2022c).

² European Commission, European IP Helpdesk Service (2021).

³ European IP Helpdesk (2022c).

⁴ See p. 87 of European Commission (2024).

⁵ See p. 87 of European Commission (2024).

⁶ See the relevant section, 'Seeking support beyond the project', for an explanation of the HRP and related support tools.

In addition, regulations in Horizon Europe state that any exploitation taking place in non-associated third countries must be accompanied by a justification of how this exploitation is still in the EU's interest¹.

Obligation to disseminate. The beneficiaries must disseminate their results as soon as feasible, in a publicly available format, although subject to any restrictions arising from concerns regarding the adequate protection of intellectual property, security rules or legitimate interests. Nevertheless, a partner that intends to disseminate its results must inform and give appropriate notice for objection to other consortium partners before disseminating project results (30 days in advance, unless agreed otherwise in the CA).

Beneficiaries are requested to make their scientific publications available as Open Access publications, and grant access to their data as open as possible and only as closed as necessary. Project partners must ensure open access to peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to their results, in particular ensuring that publications are available through scientific publications and repositories that provide immediate open access under Creative Commons or equivalent licenses. Partners (or authors) must retain sufficient intellectual property rights to comply with the open access requirements².

Pathways to impact and reporting. Horizon Europe guidelines introduced the following new methods to monitor and assess a consortium's plan and efforts to valorise the knowledge and results from the project in the long run³.

- "Pathways to Impact" is a way to monitor impact pathways for KERs and plan concrete steps towards exploitation. It consists of steps towards the achievement of the expected impacts of the project over time, after its end. From the definition of the project's KERs, such steps comprise communication, dissemination, and exploitation activities, leading to the expected outcomes and ultimately to wider scientific, economic, and societal impacts.
- Continuous dissemination and exploitation (D&E) reporting templates. While beneficiaries are no longer mandated to fill in part B for D&E, the adapted templates for HE are designed to capture a clear picture of KERs and their ownership, the number of patents projects apply to, etc.
- Post-grant surveys. Two years after the end of the grant, beneficiaries will need to report on their progress, needs and obstacles on their path towards exploitation.

(Joint) ownership. Particular emphasis should be given to the management of ownership of key project results. While the GA states that results are owned by the beneficiary that generates them, in the collaborative environment of a HE research project two or more partners may jointly contribute to an individual result. In these cases, the IP is jointly owned by different partners, who should therefore agree on the ownership terms through a Joint Ownership Agreement. In addition, they must agree on appropriate and shared strategies for the management, protection, and exploitation of the jointly owned results⁴.

Granting of access rights. HE rules also mandate the obligation of beneficiaries to grant access to other consortium partners to the knowledge they bring to the project or the generated results

¹ European IP Helpdesk (2022c).

² See article 17 of the Horizon Europe's Model GA in European Commission (2024).

³ European IP Helpdesk (2022c).

⁴ European IP Helpdesk (2022c).

whenever such access is necessary to implement project activities or to exploit the project's collaborative results. This is discussed in more detail in the relevant section titled 'Access Rights'.

2. Overview of key Innovation Management concepts

2.1 IP and IPR

To start, it is important to make a distinction between Intellectual Property (IP) and IP rights (IPR). While Intellectual Property (IP) refers to assets, IP rights (IPR) refers to legal tools to support commercial exploitation.

More specifically, IP refers to intangible creations of the human intellect that may be protected by law. In contrast, IP rights provide the legal framework by granting exclusive rights for a specified period, allowing creators to safeguard their ideas and creations from unauthorized use or reproduction. IPRs are territorial rights, meaning that they are valid only in the jurisdictions where they have been registered¹. There are several types of IPR, a description of which can be found in the respective sections of this document.

2.2 Ownership, Inventorship and Authorship²

A second distinction must be made between the concepts of ownership, inventorship and authorship. The inventor of an innovation does not always correspond to the owner and vice versa. Moreover, the inventor is not necessarily the author.

While inventorship identifies the creator of an invention, ownership recognises the proprietary right to possess an invention. Thus, ownership gives the right to prevent others from using the IP. Authorship is used in the copyright domain, more precisely in a publication environment, in which a person – the author – has produced a piece of writing or any other specific publication.

While inventors and authors are always natural persons, owners can also be legal persons (organisations), for instance the employer of an inventor/author. It is important to note that assigning ownership to an employer does not affect inventorship or authorship.

The factors that determine whether someone is a (co-)inventor include (i) conception of the idea, (ii) material contribution to the development of the invention, and (iii) implementation of the idea into practice.

The common default regime in most national legal frameworks of EU member states that copyright from inventions and the IP created by employees belong to the organisation/employer. However, in order to avoid later disputes, it is strongly recommended that employment contracts and assignment agreements contain explicit provisions and rules on the allocation of ownership for IP rights to inventions.

2.3 Background

Background IP (BG) can be defined as data, know-how or information – including any rights – owned or licensed to a project partner prior to the start of the agreement and needed to implement the action or exploit the project's results.

The implementation of any collaborative research project requires the use of pre-existing IP (i.e., background) resulting from work carried out prior to the project, and belonging to one of the partners.

¹ European IP Helpdesk & Enterprise Europe Network (2024).

² European IP Helpdesk (2022a).

Partners shall outline the respective background that each of them will bring to the project. In the CA, project partners need to create a list of background IP, as well as specific IP they wish to exclude access to¹.

All project partners must identify the background that they brought to the project to carry out its activities. The background can be identified and agreed upon (i) within the consortium agreement, after the internal evaluation of pre-existing knowledge, (ii) in a separate agreement (“agreement on the background”), and/or (iii) in the Innovation Management deliverables. In any case, the consortium must identify the background that each project partner provides and that is imperative for successful implementation and exploitation of the project. This list of background can also be part of joint ownership agreements, and shall be kept updated during the project’s implementation phase in the respective versions of the Innovation Management deliverables.

Besides this identification, it is important to define the access rights associated to the project’s background. This is discussed in the next section.

Furthermore, it is important to define what will be considered modifications/improvements to the background. The distinction between derivative and new work is not always obvious. Therefore, ownership of the background modifications needs to be defined contractually.²

Regarding ownership, examples of common IPR ownership arrangements related to background include the following:

- That each contributing party retains the sole ownership of its background.
- Relatedly, that any modifications to such BG or derivative works based on it remain the property of the BG’s original owner (i.e., the partner that brought the BG to the project).

Furthermore, since most of the joint results will contain partner-contributed IP, the background will constitute the object of future contracts and influence the conditions for the use of the results. Therefore, it is advisable to provide contractual clauses about the use of the individually-owned background IP, besides discussing the use of the joint IP.³

2.4 Access Rights

Access rights refer to a given project partner’s right to request access to another project partner’s IP (be it BG or project results) in order to implement its project activities or exploit its own results. The rules and provisions governing access rights within the project are pre-defined in the Consortium Agreement (CA) and article 16 of the Grant Agreement (GA) of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED.

Irrespective of ownership provisions, the background that is strictly needed for carrying out the project activities or exploiting the results must be accessible to the other project partners on a royalty-free basis. Partners have the right to request access rights to the other project partners’ background and results as long as they need them to carry out the project work or to exploit the project results.⁴ More specifically, each party should grant access rights to the respective partners that need certain

¹ European IP Helpdesk (2022c).

² European IP Helpdesk (2022b).

³ European IP Helpdesk (2022b).

⁴ European Commission, European IP Helpdesk Service (2021).

background, allowing them to use it in accordance with the project's scope (usually royalty-free), and within their business activities during and after the project (usually royalties-bearing).¹

In line with this, SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's CA specifies that consortium partners have access to the background/results of other partners in case they need this knowledge (IP) to implement their own project tasks or to exploit their own results.

In addition, these access rights can be requested throughout the duration of the project and up to one year after its completion when needed to carry out the exploitation of results that incorporate such BG (unless agreed otherwise in the CA). Once requested, access rights may be exercised as long as they are needed for exploiting the results (e.g. until the background patent expires).

The following table provides an overview on the access rights regime under Horizon Europe, differentiating on the type of IP and the purpose for its use²:

Table 1. Access rights regime in Horizon Europe projects

Purpose of Access	Access to Background	Access to Results
Implementation of the project	Royalty-free, unless otherwise agreed by participants before their accession to the GA	Royalty-free
Exploitation of project results	Subject to agreement, access rights shall be granted under fair and reasonable conditions (which can be royalty-free)	

Examples of access rights clauses within the scope of collaborative research projects include the following:

- Each party grants the other parties the non-exclusive right to use its background free of charge, as long as such access is strictly necessary to implement the project actions;
- Each party grants the other parties a non-exclusive, royalty-bearing, non-transferrable right to use its background, as long as such access is strictly necessary for the other party to make, sell or otherwise exploit the project result;

2.5 Project (exploitable) results and KERs

As part of the project's innovation management it is important to map any results and assets that are generated through the implementation of project activities. Results can be defined as any tangible or intangible output generated within the project's activities, whatever their form or nature, including materials, data, knowledge or other pieces of information, whether or not they can be protected, as well as any rights attached to them, including IPR³. It must be noted that output generated outside project activities cannot be categorized as 'project results'.

In general, project results are owned by the partner that generates them. However, given the collaborative nature of the project, some results can be jointly developed by several partners. In this

¹ European IP Helpdesk (2022b).

² European IP Helpdesk (2022c).

³ See the IP Helpdesk's glossary: https://intellectual-property-helpdesk.ec.europa.eu/regional-helpdesks/european-ip-helpdesk/europe-glossary/europe-ip-glossary-r_en

case, joint ownership can arise among the contributing partners and is subject to joint ownership agreements.

In addition, it is important to highlight that results generated within the project were formally called 'foreground', while current terminology, already updated in the EC's Horizon 2020 guidelines, prefers to only make a distinction between 'background' and 'results'¹.

Nevertheless, results can be categorized in different ways. For instance, a granular result can be part of a larger (composite) result, which may be a more important outcome of the project or be more relevant for exploitation purposes.

Accordingly, one can differentiate between 'results' and 'exploitable results'. An exploitable result (ER) is a project result that meets the following two criteria: (i) has commercial, social and/or academic relevance, and (ii) can be commercialised/exploited as a standalone result. However, not all results may meet the above conditions. Furthermore, ERs ought not to be ready to be exploited right after the end of the project, even though they must hold that potential; for instance, they may require further R&D, engineering, or validation before becoming a product that can be commercialized. As mentioned before, exploitable results can be a combination of more granular project results.

Furthermore, it is important to consider the concept of 'Key Exploitable Results' or KERs, which are the main project results in terms of exploitation interest and potential². Among the various identified results generated by the project that can potentially be exploited, a prioritisation must be made to distinguish the main results as Key Exploitable Results or KERs. KERs are identified and prioritised due to their high potential to be reused and valorised (in other words, exploited) and the consortium's interest in doing so.

2.6 Exploitation

In the latest available Horizon Europe Model Grant Agreement³, *exploitation* is defined as the use of results in further research and innovation activities beyond the project, including among other things, the commercial exploitation through the creation, manufacturing, marketing or provision of products or services, the development of processes, or in standardisation activities⁴.

Therefore, exploitation refers to using a result generated in SUSTCERT4BIOBASED in other activities, with the goal to valorise the result at the organizational level and/or to maximise its impact for other stakeholders. Other ways to make use of project results include, albeit apparently out of the scope of this definition of exploitation, conducting further research or providing relevant input for future policy-making. While we argue that further R&D can be interpreted as exploitation through, for instance, the development of new processes, the publication of results in scientific publications or as policy recommendations would rather fall under the scope of 'dissemination' of results (see the relevant section below for a discussion on dissemination).

One option regarding exploitation of results is for a beneficiary to transfer the ownership of IP to one of the joint owners of such (exploitable) results or even third parties⁵.

¹ European IP Helpdesk (2019).

² European IP Helpdesk (2021).

³ European Commission (2024).

⁴ See page 85 in European Commission (2024).

⁵ European IP Helpdesk (2022c).

2.7 Dissemination

Dissemination is defined in the latest Horizon Europe model GA as “the public disclosure of the results by appropriate means, other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results, including by scientific publications in any medium.”¹.

The appropriate means for the dissemination of project results (e.g. scientific publications, publication on web sites, conferences, etc.), can be selected by project partners, always taking into consideration the Open Science requirements in Horizon Europe.

In any case, partners have to first ensure the protection of a project’s Exploitable Results and then proceed to dissemination actions of the underlying result(s). In this regard, it is important to note that certain IPR protection measures require the relevant IP to be kept confidential before registering it for protection.

Specifically in the context of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED, in order to maintain confidentiality during the project and after its conclusion, the provisions set out in the Consortium Agreement establish that, during the project and for a period of one year after its end, the dissemination of own results by one or several project parties, including but not restricted to publications and presentations, shall be governed by the procedure of Article 17.4 of the Grant Agreement and its Annex 5, Section Dissemination, subject to the following provisions.

Prior notice of any planned publication shall be given to the other Parties at least 30 calendar days before the publication. Any objection to the planned publication shall be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement by written notice to the Coordinator and to the Party or Parties proposing the dissemination within 25 calendar days after receipt of the notice. If no objection is made within the time limit stated above, the publication is permitted.

2.8 Results, outcomes and impact

Horizon Europe clearly distinguishes between results, outcomes, and impact. Results are achievements made during or shortly after the implementation of the project. Outcomes are the effects of the project in the medium term, achieved through the uptake, diffusion, and use of the results. Impacts are the effects on society, the economy, and science in the long term, enabled by the outcomes of the project. The specific time periods in which results, outcomes, and impacts are expected depend on the specific project, but typically may be three, five and seven years from the project start, respectively².

2.9 Joint ownership

Joint ownership, also called co-ownership, refers to a situation in which two or more (legal or natural) persons have proprietary shares of an asset. Joint ownership often occurs in connection with collaborative innovation and is thus of particular relevance to EU-funded programmes and any research project involving co-development of IP.³

Joint ownership of IP requires that results (e.g., research results) are jointly generated by the partners, and that the exact share of the work (i.e., of the ‘material’ contributions) cannot be

¹ See page 85 in European Commission (2024).

² European IP Helpdesk (2022c).

³ European IP Helpdesk (2022b).

determined easily, or that the final work or result is indivisible by nature.¹ In addition, joint ownership may arise with regard to all the forms of IP (e.g., patents, copyright, trademarks, trade secrets, etc.).

Partners should define the terms of the resulting joint ownership in a separate *joint ownership agreement* or, alternatively, in clauses within the more general *collaboration agreement*. However, when drafting a joint ownership agreement or a collaborative agreement, it is crucial to seek legal advice, given the complexity and technicality involved in doing so.

Exploitation rights on jointly owned assets may vary across the various relevant jurisdictions. Hence, it will be determined on the national level who, among the joint owners, can grant licenses and/or sub-licenses. Likewise, the co-owner's right to be compensated for not exploiting those assets might be differently regulated or even absent in some jurisdictions. In this context, the respective co-owners need to carefully consider the choice of applicable law and jurisdiction. Choosing a jurisdiction will allow partners to uniformly interpret their joint ownership agreement and to set common rules in case disputes among them emerge. Any national law can be selected, even though it is preferable to choose a jurisdiction that offers the highest degree of impartiality as well as a high standard of protection and efficiency. It is also advisable to select a law that is applicable to the parties' respective national systems or the core of the agreement.²

Partners should define the expectations regarding jointly created results before any research activity is carried out. In addition, if possible, partners should define co-ownership issues of the expected results by considering the following factors³:

- The allocation of the ownership shares of IP results between joint owners. One of the most common options is to equally share the results among the partners. An alternative is to divide it according to their involvement in the development of the results.
- The conditions of use of the jointly owned results (IP). Co-ownership arrangements usually grant each party an unrestricted use of the jointly owned IP. However, if restrictions were to be deemed necessary, two options can be envisaged: either (a) joint ownership is maintained with the provision of mutual restrictive conditions (e.g., use strictly necessary for research activities), or (b) the property of the entire asset – hence supporting all the related costs – is assigned to a single party who will grant licenses to the other partners on an “as-needed” basis.
- The conditions of exploitation of the joint IP, under which each co-owner can assign, license and exploit the jointly owned results. For instance, whether the other partners will receive compensation when exploiting the joint results; or any rights and obligations regarding licensing costs and income.
- The conditions for dissemination of the joint IP. To maintain secrecy on the knowledge, parties can establish confidentiality rules. For instance, joint owners can agree on limits to the disclosure of data and results, bearing in mind that dissemination can be an impediment to future IP rights registration (i.e., patents, utility models and industrial designs). Common clauses include the following: (i) that a party intending to publish any research results provides a certain period of time for the other parties to verify whether the contents of such dissemination should be kept confidential; or (ii) that confidential information shall not be disclosed, reproduced, or otherwise made available to any other third party, without the consent of the other parties, at least for a certain term (e.g., until patent applications are filed).

¹ European IP Helpdesk (2022b).

² European IP Helpdesk (2022b).

³ European IP Helpdesk (2022b).

- The management of the jointly owned results (IP). This refers to the protection, maintenance and defence of the results. Regarding IPR protection, an agreement shall include: (i) the type of protection measure, (iii) when the protection will be registered, (iii) which party will file the application and then follow the procedure, and (iv) which party will bear the costs of the IP protection and maintenance. Regarding IPR infringement and enforcement, joint owners should decide which party will be responsible for monitoring and policing the joint IP as well as assume the expenses for any infringement in connection with it. The latter can arise either because the jointly owned IP infringes a third parties' IPR or because a third party infringes the co-owned IP. In the case of IPR infringements owners can legally enforce their rights against infringers¹. However, it is also recommended to first evaluate an Alternative Dispute Resolution mechanisms (ADR) such as negotiation, mediation, expert determination, arbitration, etc.²
- Governing law and jurisdiction and alternative dispute resolution mechanisms. Such mechanisms are a rapid and cost-effective way of solving disputes in contractual relationships.

It is best practice for partners to establish, during or after the project, a separate joint ownership agreement in order to define the allocation of ownership and the terms discussed above.

As mentioned at the beginning of this document, exploitation of the project results may be done by partners directly or indirectly through another party through licensing or transfer of IPR. Hence, each joint owner can grant non-exclusive licenses to third parties to exploit the jointly-owned results (without any right to sub-license). In such case, unless otherwise agreed in the CA or the joint ownership agreement, the remaining joint owners must be given at least 45 days advance notice and fair compensation³.

Lastly, it is important to note the difference between joint ownership of collaborative results and a common exploitation of composite results belonging to multiple partners. Exploitation of co-developed results can take various forms. For instance, jointly-owned results may be exploited individually by partners who have formally decided on the allocation of ownership and IPR of the results through a joint ownership agreement. However, jointly-owned results may also be exploited collaboratively, for example through joint ventures, special-purpose vehicles, or similar types of legal entities owned by multiple parties. Such joint exploitation may also not rely on jointly-owned results; i.e. not all parties that own shares in the legal entity must also be the IPR owners of the underlying results being exploited by that entity. Compared to joint ownership, agreements on the joint exploitation of individually-owned results are a common, and often simpler, pathway to manage the IPR and exploitation of project results. The aforementioned vehicles can exploit multiple elements owned by different partners through a single entity. Partners would still need to agree on (a) the division of the proprietary shares of such entity, and on (b) how to transfer the IPR to exploit the results to this new company. Although still complex and requiring further negotiations among partners, a joint exploitation through establishing a dedicated entity may be a more realistic strategy, depending on the nature of the project results. Regarding the ownership of IPR, the new common

¹ It is recommended to utilise monitoring services, online searches, and industry networks to identify potential infringements and, if infringement is detected, to consult an IP attorney (European IP Helpdesk & Enterprise Europe Network, 2024).

² ADR are a rather simple, fast and inexpensive procedure that brings parties together with the objective to resolve disputes out-of-court. Types of ADR include negotiation, mediation, expert determination, arbitration, etc. (European IP Helpdesk & Enterprise Europe Network, 2024).

³ See article 16 of the Model GA in European Commission (2024).

entity would either become the owner of the KER through the transfer of IPR, or simply acquire a license to exploit the result. In the latter case, the partners owning the individual elements would license their technology to this entity, according to their agreed terms.

2.10 Protection of digital IP

The threat posed by copying, industrial espionage, reverse engineering and manipulation of software solutions has led companies to increasingly invest in software protection. Additionally, IPR can arise in various aspects of a webpage or social media content: Be it - in respect of the logo used, the text/images that appear, the interface design, typography, domain name, databases included or the coding which determines the way the website is laid out and formatted. Some of this may have been created by the company but some of the content may have been created by others. Particularly, if your client is using an agency, pay careful attention to the property clauses. It's important to be aware of IP considerations when creating and sharing content on webpages or social media platforms to ensure they respect the rights of others and protect their own IP. Laws and regulations regarding IP can vary by jurisdiction. For software protection, depending on the jurisdiction, explore legal options like patents, copyrights, and trade secrets¹.

¹ European IP Helpdesk & Enterprise Europe Network (2024).

3. Definitions of IP protection measures

This section will discuss in more detail the most relevant and common types of instruments that may be considered for IP protection in a research project. To provide an understanding of the different measures and their use, we will clarify their characteristics and present examples of IP assets that could be protected by them.

The effective exploitation of the innovative results developed in the frame of the project is contingent on the adequate protection of their underlying IP. Project partners shall safeguard the identified exploitable results with adequate protection schemes, which will offer adequate protection period within a suitable geographical territory. When considering IP protection, project partners must not only consider their own interests but also the interests of the whole consortium.

IP protection constitutes a tool to create value through the licensing, sale or commercialisation of IP in the form of products and services. Moreover, its utilisation is vital for a prospective commercial or industrial exploitation as it can contribute to support the branding of products and services both to customers and investors. It should be noted that an asset can be of high exploitation value even if its characteristics do not mandate IP protection; for instance, this is the case of open source results with high potential for exploitation and/or wide deployment by relevant stakeholders (e.g. publications of project findings).

The geographical territory of the IP protection will have to be agreed on by the parties in advance, based on where the IP will be used. By default, Europe is considered to be the suitable territory within which the identified ERs will be safeguarded, but it remains at the discretion of the interested parties to collectively reach an agreement with regard to this matter.

There exist different types of IPR to protect R&D results from research projects. Consequently, when considering IP protection the most appropriate protection strategy must be chosen. The selection of the most suitable form of IP protection depends on the nature and specific characteristics of the results under consideration and the objectives of the IPR owner.

For instance, copyright and related rights are commonly used for artistic works, databases, etc. The granting of such IPR does not require registration. In contrast, trade marks, patents, utility models, industrial designs, etc., are more suited for 'industrial' results and require registration. In addition, trade secrets can be used to protect 'soft' or 'intangible' IP such as know-how or confidential information.

Overall, such rights grant a monopoly on the use and/or commercialisation of the innovation for a limited amount of time, which depends on the type of protection measure. Such exclusivity can also help attract funding and investment.

However, while ownership of IPR provides exclusivity, this does not equal protection in practice. It is therefore important that results are not only protected but that IPR are managed and enforced.

3.1 Patents and utility models

A **patent** is a legal title granting its holder the right to prevent third parties from commercially exploiting an invention without the authorisation of the patent holder. Therefore, the value of a patent arises from giving its owner a monopoly.

Patents are granted for inventions that demonstrate potential for industrial application. A patent protects inventions (i.e., products or processes) offering a new technical solution or facilitating a new

way of doing something. Therefore, patents must be novel and demonstrate progress beyond the state-of-the-art. Quoting the European Patent Convention, “European patents shall be granted for any inventions, in all fields of technology, provided that they are new, involve an inventive step and are susceptible of industrial application.”¹

Patent protection requires registration, which can be filed in the patent office of choice. In return, the patent holder must disclose the invention to the public in the patent application, which requires showing how the invention functions. Some patents are granted only per country, while others give supranational protection (e.g., at the European level).

In addition, patent rights are granted for a certain period of time, generally for 10 or 20 years, depending on each legislation². Once a patent expires and the protection ends, the invention becomes part of the public domain, meaning that the patented invention becomes available for commercial exploitation, free of charge, by others³.

For patents, the inventor is also the first person with the right to be granted patent protection for their creation. In fact, a patent can only be granted to its inventor or to the person who claims ownership through the inventor.⁴

Patent owners may give permission to other parties to use the patented invention during the protected period. Moreover, they can offer a license or even sell the patent right (i.e., the ownership of the patent) to another person.

According to the European Patent Convention, mathematical methods, programs for computers or aesthetic creations, among others, are not regarded as inventions with regards to patentability⁵. Software is thus excluded from patentability to the extent that a patent application relates to a computer program “as such”. However, computer-implemented inventions, defined by the European Patent Office (EPO) as innovations that “involve computers, computer networks or other programmable apparatus, whereby at least one feature is realised by means of a [software] program”⁶, are accepted at the EPO. It is relevant to note that a computer program and a computer-implemented method are distinct from each other: while the former refers to a sequence of computer-executable instructions specifying a method, the latter refers to a method being performed on a computer.⁷ Relatedly, database management systems, defined as technical systems implemented on computers to perform the tasks of storing and retrieving data using various data structures, are considered a method that uses technical means and are therefore not excluded from patentability either.⁸

Like patents, **utility models** are exclusive rights granted for an invention (i.e., a product or a process) that either provides a new way of doing something or offers a new technical solution to a problem.

¹ See art. 52 in European Patent Office (2020).

² European IP Helpdesk & Enterprise Europe Network (2024).

³ See p. 17 in WIPO Intellectual Property Handbook (2008).

⁴ European IP Helpdesk (2022a).

⁵ See art. 52 in European Patent Office (2020).

⁶ See Part F – Chapter IV-10 in European Patent Office (2024).

⁷ See Part G – Chapter II-17 in European Patent Office (2024).

⁸ See Part G – Chapter II-21 in European Patent Office (2024).

In addition, in order to obtain protection, registration must be granted. However, utility models are not available in every country¹.

Also referred to as a “petty patent”, a utility model is an exclusive right granted to a right holder, for an invention that does not fulfil patentability requirements (e.g., because it is a minor improvement of an existing product) but may still have an important role in a local innovation system. Utility models are also considered to be particularly suited for products that have a short commercial life. Once granted, this type of protection allows the right holder to prevent others from commercially using the protected invention, without their authorisation, for a limited period.

In the EU, utility models can be granted at the national level in some of the Member States, but there exists no European-wide utility model protection. The eligibility requirements also vary across countries.

Generally, this type of protection is subject to less stringent requirements and procedures than patents, and offers a shorter term of protection. However, given that they are designed to respond to local needs, requirements and protection duration vary between different jurisdictions.

3.2 Trademarks and Industrial designs

Trademarks are signs capable of distinguishing the goods or services of one enterprise from those of others (e.g., its competitors). Therefore, they offer an exclusive right over the use of a sign in relation to the goods and services it represents.

Examples of such signs include combination of words or letters, drawings, symbols, and even sounds or fragrances, among others. This type of IPR confers an exclusive right to the use of the registered trademark. While the trademark lasts for 10 years, it is renewable indefinitely². In contrast, a patent always expires.

The aim of trademark law is to distinguish between products of different manufacturers. There are different types of trademarks, such as word mark, figurative mark, word-picture mark, sound mark, shape mark, colour mark (the list is not exhaustive). Trade mark law protects the design only indirectly. Neither novelty nor a creative level of creation are necessary. But there are also disadvantages: Firstly, protection is limited to the goods and services designated in the trademark register, and secondly, for a trademark that has not been used for more than 5 years, anyone can apply for its cancellation for the unused goods and services³.

Lastly, protection for trademarks can be obtained through registration at national, EU or international levels. In addition, the trademark right holder may license the trademark to a third party, specifying the conditions in a license agreement.

Industrial designs can also be protected by exclusive rights. Design protection protects the two- or three-dimensional external appearance of a whole product or a part thereof. More specifically, a design refers to “the appearance of the whole or a part of a product resulting from the features of, in particular, the lines, contours, colours, shape, texture and/ or materials of the product itself and/or

¹ European IP Helpdesk & Enterprise Europe Network (2024).

² European IP Helpdesk & Enterprise Europe Network (2024).

³ European IP Helpdesk & Enterprise Europe Network (2024).

its ornamentation.”¹ Examples include the design of vehicles, furniture or clothing, as well as product packaging, equipment and other graphic symbols.

For this type of IPR to be granted in the EU, the design must be registered in the industrial property office of a Member State, and it must demonstrate novelty and singularity or ‘individual character’. A design is considered new if no identical design has been made available to the public before the filing of the application for registration. Individual character requires that the impression the design produces on the informed user differs from the impression produced by any existing design.

3.3 Trade secrets and Confidentiality (or non-disclosure) agreements

A **trade secret** is a type of IP that encompasses confidential, proprietary information (such as manufacturing processes, formulas, techniques, customer lists, marketing strategies, software algorithms, data and more).

Unlike patents, copyrights, or trademarks, trade secrets rely on maintaining their secrecy. To qualify as a trade secret, the information must be confidential (i.e., unknown or not readily accessible to the public or competitors) and have economic value. In addition, the owner of the trade secret must take reasonable efforts to keep the information confidential, for instance through non-disclosure agreements or access controls².

Any confidential business information providing a competitive advantage to an enterprise can be considered a trade secret. Therefore, it can include know-how, technical knowledge (potentially protectable as a patent), but also business and commercial data such as lists of customers, business plans, recipes or manufacturing processes.

Contrary to other protection modalities, trade secrets are protected without any procedural formalities, and can be protected for an unlimited period of time. Trade secrets offer a lesser degree of protection compared to patents, yet they serve as a valuable method for preserving proprietary business information that may not qualify to be protected by patents. Right holders may sell or license the protected information and its protection. However, protection for trade secrets hinges on the secrecy of the information; if disclosed publicly, trade secret protection can be instantaneously lost. Lastly, trade secrets are enforced through actions for breach of confidence or, if a non-disclosure agreement or clause exists, breach of contract.

Confidentiality agreements, also known as non-disclosure agreements (NDAs), are contracts that provide protection to organisations wishing to disclose valuable information and ideas to other parties in confidence. These written agreements establish the obligation of the recipient (i.e. the legal person to whom the information is disclosed) to not disclose the information to third parties. Therefore, they provide an assurance that confidential information will be used only for the agreed purposes and will not be used or revealed to third parties without consent.

Therefore, confidentiality agreements are crucial for inventors or other parties willing to protect confidential information. This is also the case for participants in collaborative R&I projects, where the exchange of valuable, confidential information is necessary to set up, implement the project, in addition to exploit its results.

¹ European Parliament, Council of the European Union (1998).

² European IP Helpdesk & Enterprise Europe Network (2024).

Confidentiality agreements can protect project results which represent confidential information that, if kept secret, can offer an organisation a competitive advantage and thus be part of wider exploitation efforts, e.g. in the development of technology, products or processes. Examples of information commonly covered by NDAs include a product design or a business idea.

In order for a confidentiality agreement to be legally enforceable, the information must be secret, hold commercial value, and the owner must have taken reasonable steps to protect its confidentiality.

While NDAs are not categorized as IPR, they are valuable instruments to protect sensitive information or trade secrets. NDAs generally incorporate contractual terms that establish compensation if a breach of confidentiality occurs.

3.4 Copyright and Creative Commons Licenses

Copyright law protects authorship understood as the expression of an original work created by an author.

The general rule is that the author is the first owner of the copyrighted material and has the right to decide the type of use that other persons can make of his or her works.¹ Thus, copyright represents the IPR that authors have over their work.

Copyright generally applies to literary, musical, artistic works, but also to other intellectual works such as computer programs, databases, advertisements, maps, and technical drawings. Copyright can also protect software or information stored on hardware and used by computer systems to execute operations, including algorithms, program codes and graphical interfaces.²

In the EU, copyright protection grants the following exclusive rights: (i) economic rights, guaranteeing control over the work and remuneration for its use through selling or licensing; and moral rights, usually protecting an author's rights to claim authorship and the right of being cited as the author (i.e., right of attribution) and the right to refuse a modification of the work (i.e., right to the integrity of the work)³, as well as the right to withdraw the work from publication.⁴

Unlike other IPR measures, copyright protection arises automatically upon the creation of the work, without need for registration. Nevertheless, it is a common practice for organisations to register copyrighted works with ad hoc services offered by some national IP offices or private organisations.⁵

The decisive criterion for a work to qualify for copyright is based on originality; quality or functional novelty are irrelevant. Consequently, copyright can also apply to original software outputs (e.g., source code or a user interface) and databases. Nevertheless, copyright does not protect ideas nor the functional aspects of a computer program.

Copyright gives the owner the exclusive right to use a work - with some exceptions. When a person creates an original work that is recorded on a physical medium (e.g. audiovisual works: TV programmes, series, films and online videos; written works: lectures, articles, books and musical

¹ European IP Helpdesk (2022a).

² European IP Helpdesk & Enterprise Europe Network (2024).

³ European Union – Your Europe (2023).

⁴ European IP Helpdesk (2022a).

⁵ European IP Helpdesk (2022a).

compositions; video games and computer software, and many more), that person automatically holds the copyright in that work¹.

Copyright law is largely harmonized in the EU through 13 directives and 2 regulations. In the EU, copyright protects IP until 70 years after the (last surviving) author's death. Outside of the EU, the duration of copyright protection varies but it lasts until at least 50 years after the author's death.²

Creative Commons (CC) Licenses. CC licenses are a free, universally accessible and standardised manner to grant copyright permissions for creative and academic works. CC licenses are free of charge and do not require creators or other rights holders to register with a Creative Commons organisation to assign a CC license to their work³.

CC licenses are copyright licenses and depend on the existence of a copyright to work; as such, they work worldwide and last as long as applicable copyright lasts. CC licenses are appropriate for creators willing to make their work available to the public for limited kinds of uses. However, they are not recommended for IP owners willing to keep all of their rights under copyright law⁴.

Different types of CC licenses exist, with distinct levels of restrictiveness regarding the reuse of the protected results. For instance, 'Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs' are the most restrictive type of CC license, only allowing third parties to share the licensed work as long as the owner is credited, without allowing them to change the work in any way nor use it commercially. On the other hand, 'Attribution' licenses are the most permissive type of CC license, letting third parties distribute, remix, adapt, and build upon the licensed work, even for commercial purposes, as long as the owner is credited for the original creation. Thus, they are recommended for owners that want to achieve the largest dissemination and reuse of their licensed work.

3.5 Domain names

Domain Names are the typographical characters corresponding to registered IP addresses, which are used to identify a particular website on the internet.

Although a domain name is unique and may be a valuable commercial asset, a domain name registration is not considered as a type of IPR.⁵

However, when the domain name contains a trademark, it can then be considered as protected intellectual property. If one has a registered trademark, other parties are not allowed to register that trademark as a domain name.⁶

¹ European IP Helpdesk & Enterprise Europe Network (2024).

² European Union – Your Europe (2023).

³ Creative Commons (2023).

⁴ Creative Commons (2023).

⁵ See the Glossary of the IP Helpdesk: https://intellectual-property-helpdesk.ec.europa.eu/regional-helpdesks/european-ip-helpdesk/europe-glossary_en

⁶ DNS Belgium (n.d.).

3.6 Sui Generis Protection (database rights)

European sui generis protection is applied with the aim to protect the content of a database, preventing the extraction and/or reuse of the whole or substantial part of its content. This type of protection is relevant when the structure of the database is not an original creation – the structure of a database may be protected by copyright.

To benefit from this right, the maker of the database must prove to have made a substantial investment – in terms of financial, material and/or human resources – in either obtaining, verifying or presenting the database content.

Database protection can apply to both electronic and non-electronic (i.e. paper) databases as well as both static and dynamic databases. The sui generis right protects, as an intangible asset, the results of the substantial investment carried out towards the methodical and systematic classification of independent data.

The sui generis database right protects the content of your database. As such, it can prevent the extraction and/or reuse of the whole or a substantial part of the database's content. However, this right does not affect existing copyright protection which may apply to the contents of the database.

In the EU, the terms of sui generis protection are defined in Directive 96/9/EC. Protection extends to systematically or methodically arranged collections of independent works, data, or materials that exhibit originality through the selection or arrangement of their content. Protection is granted for 15 years, starting either from the creation date of the database or from the moment it was made publicly available. Lastly, the right can be transferred or licensed to third parties and applies regardless of the database's eligibility for copyright protection or other rights.

4. Strategy throughout the project's lifecycle

Relevant IP aspects arise throughout the lifecycle of a project: from the conceptualisation stage, during its activities, and even beyond its implementation through the potential exploitation and commercialisation of its results.

Before the start of the project, it is essential to define the existing IP that is brought to the project by the partners (i.e., the background). It is also important to monitor the patent landscape. During the project implementation, partners must identify relevant IP elements and discuss possible IP protection methods. After the end of the project, it is crucial to discuss and agree on (joint) exploitation strategies and pathways, as well as studying possible IP ownership arrangements and defining the related responsibilities for managing IPR protection. It is also crucial to explore potential agreements related to licensing or transfer of IPR.

At the strategic level, the Innovation Management approach in SUSTCER4BIOBASED is aligned with the five pillars of IP management in Horizon Europe¹, with the aim of addressing the diverse IP issues that typically arise at different stages of a collaborative Horizon Europe project.

Figure 1. Strategic pillars of IP Management in Horizon Europe research projects

IP awareness. At the start of the project, or ideally even before its start, it is crucial for the consortium to be – or become – aware of the relevant IP policies, rules and agreements that apply to the project and its prospective results, given the nature of the project's R&I activities and the technologies it deals with. To this end, the present report provides a thorough understanding of the relevant IP and Innovation Management concepts, rules and processes for HE, based on an up-to-date review of existing EC guidelines and trainings. It also identifies the relevant literature and material that consortium partners wishing to explore these aspects further can use.

IP created. Also before and at the start of the project, consortium partners must identify and agree on which pre-existing IP (i.e., background) is to be shared among consortium partners and under what terms and conditions it becomes available for use both during the project as well as after its end if needed for project implementation or results exploitation purposes. As the project progresses, the IP created needs to be defined; an Innovation Management approach such as the one presented

¹ See European IP Helpdesk (2022c).

in this report needs to be put in place to ensure the capture of these results and facilitate agreements on ownership and relative contributions, as well as on who will manage the results and how.

IP assessment. IP assessment refers to the process of identifying, evaluating and analysing IP assets, as well as identifying the relevant IPR related to the identified IP. Hence, during the project's implementation phase, the commercial and scientific exploitation potential of the results must be assessed. Results are also assessed with regard to their readiness (e.g., their expected technological readiness level). In addition, protection strategies for KERs should be defined. If relevant, a preliminary assessment of the IP landscape should be performed, which may include a freedom-to-operate analysis and patentability checks. Altogether, this IP assessment will help in making informed decisions regarding the management, exploitation and/or protection of project results.

IP protection. In addition, appropriate measures for the protection of results should be put in place, when relevant to support a financially-sensible commercial exploitation. It is relevant to consider that the costs of protection are eligible costs in HE projects. Protection measures includes applicable IPR, trade secrets, trademarks, etc. Towards a smooth valorisation of IP, it must also be ensured that specific provisions are put in place regarding access rights to results in order to safeguard the interests of the IP owners while at the same time allowing other project partners to exploit project results.

IP valorisation. Towards the end of the project, as the key exploitable results of the project are developed, the focus must shift to the planning of tailored exploitation and dissemination pathways for these KERs, with the aim to ensure their long-term sustainability and impact. IP valorisation includes project activities as well as post-project ones. As outlined at the beginning of this document, HE beneficiaries are expected to exploit the KERs they own after the project. When relevant, IP valorisation also includes IPR management activities, including potential IP transfers (under agreed terms and conditions) and agreements for post-project efforts to maintain and potentially enforce the IP protection (including, for example, cost and revenue sharing agreements).

This strategic approach is also aligned with the slightly different 6-pillar IP strategy identified in previous material from the IP helpdesk¹. The main difference rests on the split of the IP valorisation phase in two: on the one hand, dissemination and exploitation actions and on the other hand, post-project management activities.

Overall, the present innovation management strategy relies on an iterative approach that consists of a continuous monitoring of project developments in order to identify any IP elements and the respective IPR owners and adequate protection measures. At the more practical level, the followed approach will be tailored to the needs of the project and the needs of the IPR management strategy at each stage of it. This tailored methodology, comprising a series of guidelines and templates, will support all consortium partners in identifying and managing in a structured way the BG and the (exploitable) results of the project, assessing relevant protection measures and agreements to enable the successful exploitation of the project's results. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's methodology is thoroughly explained in the relevant chapter of this report (see 'Methodology').

Below we explain in more detail the entire innovation management strategy throughout the different relevant stages within the project. The relevant timeline covers a period spanning pre-project and post-project stages, besides, naturally, a project's implementation period.

¹ European Commission, European IP Helpdesk Service (2021).

4.1 GA preparation stage

Both the Grant Agreement (GA) and the Consortium Agreement (CA) discuss several issues related to IPR. Their unique provisions represent a reference point for IPR issues that might present themselves during and after the project. These provisions can also facilitate any further advancements regarding IPR actions that project partners wish to put in place.

Grant Agreement. The GA constitutes a contract which sets out the key rules and conditions of the project and is agreed upon between the European Commission (EC) and the project partners. It represents the main contractual basis for the project, including several fundamental provisions referring to IPR, under which the management of the project's IP is regulated. For instance, it defines access rights and obligations related to the background brought to the project. In addition, the Grant Agreement defines issues concerning the ownership and protection of the project's generated results, as well as their exploitation and dissemination outcomes. Finally, transferability and access rights to results are also defined in the project's GA.

Consortium Agreement. The CA constitutes a contract among the consortium partners that aims to define rights and obligations for the purposes of carrying out the project's foreseen actions and activities. To complement the provisions outlined in the GA, the CA addresses specific IP provisions as well as provisions for settlement of internal disputes. Regarding IP provisions, the CA discusses, among others, aspects of confidentiality, background selection, use of IP generated parallel to the project (sideground), ownership/joint ownership of results, legal protection of results (IPR), access rights, and procedures for dissemination of results¹.

The Consortium Agreement minimises the probability of later disputes as it provides rules and responsibilities to be followed during the project as well the delineation of access rights to be granted to the partners in the context of the project. In addition, it outlines the rights and responsibilities among the consortium members concerning IPR issues. For instance, the CA covers the following IPR-related aspects:

- *Results*, sets out provisions on ownership and joint ownership of results, as well as on their transfer and dissemination.
- *Access Rights* clarifies the access rights governing principles along with the access rights for the exploitation and dissemination purposes. It also states specific provisions for access rights to the software.
- *Background included* presents a preliminary list of usable background identified at the pre-project stage.

4.2 Implementation stage

During the implementation stage of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED, IP handling procedures are applied among the consortium partners in order to properly identify and manage all project results and assets. With this goal in mind, it is important to establish a dedicated IP monitoring methodology that shall be followed from the early stages of the project and throughout its lifespan. As presented in more detail in the ['Methodology'] section, we established mechanisms to guarantee that IP information is reliably and timely captured.

Overall, the IPR management strategy of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED consisted of the following interconnected and iterative steps: (i) **identification of any further background IP** and definition of access rights among partners within the project; (ii) **identification of the results** generated under

¹ European IP Helpdesk (2022c).

each project task; (iii) prioritisation of results to **identify the project's Key Exploitable Results**; (iv) plotting of the corresponding **(co-)owners and their type of exploitation interest**, along with the contributing partners to each result; (v) **definition of IPR protection measures, rights of use and exploitation pathways per partner** for the defined KERs; (vi) discussion of the KERs' **value proposition to the main target stakeholders**; and, lastly, (vii) the descriptions of each **partner's individual post-project valorisation plans** to make use of the overall knowledge gained during the project and the assets developed in it.

The initial version of the Innovation Strategy focused on the identification of the knowledge brought to the project by the different partners and the preliminary mapping of project results and their IPR. More specifically, at the initial implementation stages of the project, the Innovation Strategy of SUSTCER4BIOBASED identified the background IP of the project and, to the extent possible, the main expected ERs. Access rights to the BG were also defined. As the project evolved, the initial focus on BG knowledge evolved to put more relative emphasis on the identification of ERs, with the respective discussions on asset ownership, access rights and IP protection, together with preliminary expected exploitation interests and pathways.

As the project advanced, the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Innovation Management approach emphasised the handling of IP protection issues related to the specific results that are of strategic importance to the project, in order to facilitate the exploitation of its key exploitable results, including their further development. Accordingly, during the later stages of the project's implementation, the focus shifted to the consideration of KERs and the pathways to guarantee their sustainability and wider impact in post-project stages.

By the end of the project, the consortium ensured that the identification of IP elements, together with their ownership, protection conditions and exploitation plans, is exhaustive and aligned. Lastly, at this stage, it must also be clear how the KERs add value to their main target stakeholders.

4.2.1 *Main roles*

Within SUSTCERT4BIOBASED, clear roles and clear responsibilities have been established with the aim to efficiently and effectively carry out the Innovation Management strategy defined throughout this deliverable.

The **Exploitation Manager** (White Research) is responsible for defining the Innovation Management strategy of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED. This includes writing the respective reports and ensuring that all the discussed IP elements and strategies are captured and defined, respectively. In addition, the Exploitation Manager guides consortium partners in order to commonly establish the most adequate and efficient IPR strategies based on the nature of the newly identified assets and the purposes of the consortium concerning the exploitation of this asset. Finally, the Exploitation Manager also assumes a mediation role in case of IP conflicts, helping the involved partners find a mutually agreeable solution (including written agreements whenever necessary) and always in line with the provisions of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's CA.

The exploitation manager also plays a role in identifying potential risks and matching expectations among consortium partners, which is a pre-requisite for developing the necessary trust environment for the exploitation of collaborative results. The nature of collaborative international projects gives rise to interdependencies among consortium partners and their work. In turn, these interdependencies entail potential challenges from the alignment of different partners' cultures and objectives. This is particularly the case when both research organisations and SMEs/industry actors are present; while the former are driven and rewarded by publishing their findings, the latter are driven by increasing their competitiveness and growth, which can be hampered when publishing

results before adequate protection has been secured¹. The increased focus on Open Science practices in HE increases the need to appropriately address potentially conflicting expectations by taking into account the different interests and objectives of all partners. To this end, partners shall strive to find a clear collective purpose and vision regarding the project's expected outcomes.

Throughout the entire project's duration, the Exploitation Manager will be in close communication with the **Project Coordinator** and the Steering Committee, as well as seek their support when necessary, in order to ensure the optimal management of all IP assets.

All partners. The efficient management of IP in a collaborative project can only be achieved through an active, participatory process, in which all consortium partners contribute to the timely identification and assessment of the IP (strategies) arising from their project activities and their respective organisational interests. Therefore, each partner is responsible for: (i) identifying the IP they are bringing as background for the implementation of the project and/or the exploitation of its results; (ii) capturing the results stemming from their work in the project; (iii) assessing the exploitability of such results and the most suitable protection avenues; and ultimately (iv) safeguarding their exploitation by identifying and taking any necessary actions during or after the project (e.g. deciding on ownership issues, drafting IP sharing or transfer agreements, maintaining protection measures, etc.). Project partners can rely on the support of the Exploitation Manager and the structured tools prepared as part of the project's Innovation Management methodology in order to carry out these responsibilities in a time-efficient and structured manner.

Naturally, Work Package and task leaders play a crucial role in the monitoring of the results generated under their respective WPs and tasks. Consequently, they are responsible for informing the Innovation partners to inform and consult with the Exploitation Manager and the Coordinator before deciding Management of the IPR-relevant aspects within their WPs and tasks, especially when joint ownership aspects may be present.

Finally, it is good practice for whether to protect a KER stemming from their activities – particularly when joint ownership is present.

4.3 Post-project stage

This deliverable, D6.8, represents the final version of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Exploitation and Sustainability Plan, submitted at the formal conclusion of the project in M36. It outlines the consortium's approach to utilising the project's exploitable results, including detailed descriptions, sectors of application, and the timeline for their exploitation. This work will guide partners willing to sign an IPR Agreement by providing an understanding of the specifying partners' contribution to each asset, presenting a clear split of IPR among the consortium, and facilitating a clear-cut exploitation route that has been agreed upon by the consortium. D6.8 also details the activities planned to support the dissemination and exploitation of the project's achievements and the measures put in place to ensure the long-term sustainability of its results. Finally, D6.8 outlines the advanced strategy for exploitation and management of IP and sustainability beyond the project's completion, including the concrete commercialisation streams chosen by the consortium.

4.3.1 *Seeking support beyond the project: Available support services from the EC*

A plethora of publicly-financed services are available to Horizon Europe beneficiaries for support with the IPR management or the exploitation of project results beyond the grant's lifetime.

¹ European IP Helpdesk (2022c).

The **Horizon Results Platform (HRP)** is the European Commission's corporate platform promoting Key Exploitable Results (KERs) of Horizon Europe projects. It is free-of-charge and hosted on the Funding & Tenders portal. To support the exploitation of KERs, the HRP provides matchmaking opportunities through an ecosystem of partners, access to investors, as well as training from mentors and coaches.

The **European IP Helpdesk** is a free-of-charge IP support service from the EC. Its goal is to support European SMEs and beneficiaries of EU-funded research projects manage their IP through the following services, among others¹:

- Training and awareness raising
- Resources library
- An Ambassadors Scheme: A group of EEN experts on IP, tech transfer and innovation that provide basic IP training

The **Horizon Results Booster** is an initiative of the EC which supports projects eager to go beyond their Dissemination and Exploitation (D&E) obligations - steering research towards strong societal impact and concretizing the value of R&I activity for societal challenges. The Horizon Results Booster offers 3 types of services²:

- Portfolio Dissemination & Exploitation Strategy
- Tailor made support services to develop a business plan
- Assistance, coaching and mentoring for go-to-market activities

The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project applied for and received support from the Horizon Results Booster services for exploitation.

The **Enterprise Europe Network (EEN)**. The EEN is a large network that supports SMEs with their innovation and international growth ambitions. The European Commission launched the Enterprise Europe Network in 2008. It is funded through the Single Market Programme and implemented by the EC's European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency (EISMEA). The main activities of the EEN for business, technology and R&D partnering are the following³:

- Internationalisation advisory services. Identifying intellectual property assets of the company, IP due diligence, market analysis, IP cost/benefit analysis, IP valuation, IP audit, etc.
- Partnering opportunities database (POD)
- Brokerage (match-making) events, company missions, trade fairs. It helps find new business partners, build up business relationships and start cooperation
- Collaborative R&D&I projects

¹ European IP Helpdesk & Enterprise Europe Network (2024). Intellectual Property (IP) Handbook: Providing IP Guidance through the EEN Client Journey. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union

² European IP Helpdesk & Enterprise Europe Network (2024). Intellectual Property (IP) Handbook: Providing IP Guidance through the EEN Client Journey. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union

³ European IP Helpdesk & Enterprise Europe Network (2024). Intellectual Property (IP) Handbook: Providing IP Guidance through the EEN Client Journey. Luxembourg: Publications Office of the European Union

5. Methodology

To facilitate the process described in the ‘Strategy’ chapter – ‘Implementation stage’ section, WHITE developed a series of guidelines and templates to monitor and regularly update the definition of IP elements and protection and exploitation strategies.

5.1 Identification of Background IP

The first step towards the definition of all the relevant IP elements of the project is to identify the background knowledge or IP (BG) that SUSTCERT4BIOBASED partners brought to the project from external or previous activities.

Our methodology to comprehensively identify all the BG contributed to the project relies on an iterative process. First, an initial mapping of BG is done when drafting the project’s Consortium Agreement. Subsequently, through the use of the offline template illustrated below, partners are asked to fill in the relevant information at different stages of the implementation phase. This iterative approach allows to update the list of BG by adding any new IP brought into the project by a given project partner.

The template below allows to compile data for all the main relevant elements related to the project’s BG in a standardised manner. Once the table is filled in, the compiled information will enable the understanding of the nature of the BG, its use within SUSTCERT4BIOBASED, and the different IPR considerations including protection and access rights, more specifically the conditions to use within and beyond the project by partners and/or third parties.

BG #	Description	Contributing partner(s)	Intended use in project	Type of IP protection	Access rights: Conditions to use within the project	Access rights: Conditions to use beyond the project
BG1						
BG2						
BG3						
BG4						
BG5						

The first column of the template assigns a number to each identified BG element, facilitating the mapping of relations between this BG and the project results that will be identified in the following steps. The second column of the template, a short description of the BG can be provided. In the third column, the name of the partner(s) who contribute this BG can be indicated, potentially distinguishing between primary and auxiliary contributors. The fourth column is intended determine how the BG will be used within the project, for instance its role within the activities or a specific task or WP to enable partners to perform certain activities or to help them achieve the task’s goals. The fifth column allows partners to specify the relevant IP protection measures for the BG in terms of the instruments defined in section [‘3. Definitions of IP protection measures’]. The last two columns allow project partners to indicate the conditions for the use of the BG within the project or beyond it, specifying whether there are any restrictions to use the BG and, if so, the conditions that apply to other project

partners and/or third parties. Examples of access rights and conditions include 'free to use', 'free to use under certain conditions', 'subject to charges/fees', etc.

5.2 Identification of (Key) Exploitable Results and IPR protection measures and actions

5.2.1 Identification of (Key) Exploitable Results

A crucial aspect in the project's innovation management methodology is the identification of the project's exploitable results, an exercise which is conducted, once again, collaboratively by project partners with the guidance of structured templates and guidelines prepared by the Innovation Manager. The following templates were circulated offline, using several iterations in order to timely identify early results arising from project activities as well as to update, validate and extend the list of results in parallel with the project's developments throughout its implementation phase.

The first step consists in the identification, classification and description of project results with exploitable potential. In practice, project partners are asked to provide the following information using the table below:

- The type of result, namely whether the result is a main project result or a secondary result. This step allows for a prioritization between exploitable results (ERs) and key exploitable results (KERs), an important decision that will need to be validated, as it will affect the follow-up steps regarding exploitation and IPR management.
- The specific project activities that gave rise to the result, e.g. the specific tasks or WPs.
- Other ERs included within the result, in case the given result is a composite one that incorporates multiple project results.
- The sector of application of the result (e.g., the Textile sector or the Bioeconomy sector).
- A short description of the result that has been achieved.

ER # and Name	Type of result	Related project activities	ERs included (if any)	Sector of application	Description
ER1: Name					
ER2: Name					
ER3					
ER4					
ER5					
ER6					

5.2.2 Identification of IPR ownership and relevant protection measures

Once the different project ERs have been identified and classified, we can proceed to conduct a deeper analysis of ownership and IPR aspects for the those ERs prioritised as main project results or KERs. To this end, the following table is used to identify the main elements required to engage in ownership and IPR management discussions and decisions. More specifically, the following new data can be compiled in a standardised and structure manner by using the additional template below:

- The names of contributing partners to the development of the KER, distinguishing between main contributor(s) and supporting ones. This identification will be useful to determine the owner(s) of the result.
- The (proposed) owner(s) of the KER. This decision will need to be taken in consensus among the different developing partners, with the guidance of the Exploitation Manager. Ownership decisions may be made at a later stage of the project, once the result is fully developed and the relevant discussions among concerned partners have taken place.
- Feasible types of IPR protection mechanisms (e.g., patents, copyright, etc.). Different types of protection mechanisms may apply to a specific result; once again, the final decision on the chosen mechanism will need to be done in agreement among the owners and with the guidance of the Exploitation Manager.
- The geographical coverage and jurisdiction of choice. As explained in previous sections, certain protection measures allow the IPR owners to choose where to register the novel IP. Different measures also offer distinct ranges of geographical coverage. This decision will be important to define the practical post-project exploitation actions for a given result.
- Any related background IP that was used to develop the specific innovation or result. Here, a reference to a BG element identified in the list of BG IP can be introduced.
- The access rights to the result by other partners or third parties, differentiating between (i) conditions to use within the project (i.e., for the implementation of project activities) and conditions to exploit and disseminate the result, whether there are any usage restrictions or not (e.g., free to use, subject to charges like license fees, etc.).

ER number	Key Exploitable Result (KER)	Developing Partner(s)	Proposed Owner(s)	Relevant IPR protection mechanism	Geographical coverage and jurisdiction for registration	Related BG#	Conditions for use	Conditions for dissemination and exploitation
ER1	KER Name							
ER2								
ER3								
ER4								

Special consideration must be given to jointly-owned results, given the additional complexity in the management of the IPR for these results. Therefore, the last step in the definition of IPR protection measures for KERs concerns solely those KERs for which, using the previous table, it was decided that multiple partners would claim ownership of the IPR. When co-ownership of results applies, it is important to allocate the ownership shares among the involved partners. In addition, it is important to discuss any terms for post-project ownership or any potential IPR transfers among co-owners, as such agreements may facilitate the exploitation of the results. Examples of such agreements include the definition of which parties shall bear the related costs from IPR management, the transfer of ownership rights to another co-owner. Next, it is also important to define each co-owner’s responsibilities regarding IP protection actions (e.g., filing an application for a patent) as well as the maintenance, monitoring and enforcement of such protection, all of which may entail non-negligible costs. Lastly, co-owners can also choose the applicable law and jurisdiction in case of disputes. The following table, along with the accompanying guidelines and examples provided by White Research, was used to guide partners in this exercise, making sure that partners engage in the necessary discussions in the presence of jointly-owned results and that all relevant aspects discussed in this paragraph are addressed. Ultimately, the purpose of this template was to gather information that will be useful for partners when preparing their joint ownership agreements.

Jointly-owned IP (e.g., KER #)	Allocation of shares among joint owners	Terms for post-project ownership, IPR transfer, etc.	IP protection and maintenance responsibilities	IP monitoring and enforcement responsibilities	Governing jurisdiction and dispute resolution
KER1: Name					
KER2					
KER N					

“It is the role of the Exploitation Manager to consolidate this input and present the findings in a structured, clear and consistent way. When the input collection is done offline and data is provided individually by each partner, inconsistencies between their inputs are possible. Specifically for jointly developed results, uncertainties subject to further discussion are prone to arise. Therefore, such inconsistencies or uncertainties need to be identified and addressed in validation rounds with the relevant partners.”

5.2.3 Specific IPR protection and pre-exploitation actions in the short run

Having identified the right owners and protection measures for each of the project’s results, the next step is to define the most relevant immediate post-project actions that will be necessary to ensure that such protection is achieved and that the subsequent exploitation of the results is enabled. To this end, the following table aims to guide result owners with the definition of specific short-term actions related to IPR (e.g., to apply for the proper protection measures or to put into practice any agreements regarding joint ownership).

In addition, this template may be used, whenever relevant, to create a roadmap of the most important and immediate actions to ensure the exploitation readiness of the KER (e.g., further development, testing and/or validation, delineation of a business plan, or the license or transfer of IPR) and the compliance with open science mandates (e.g., dissemination measures such as uploading results in an adequate repository).

With the guidance of the Exploitation Manager and dedicated discussions whenever necessary, partners used the following table to define any relevant actions as well as their related costs, responsible partners and the estimated time of implementation.

ER number	Key Exploitable Result (KER)	Action type	Action's description	Estimated costs (outside project budget)	Responsible partner(s)	Timeline
ER1						
ER2						
ER3						

5.3 Identification of exploitation interests and actions

This section comprises a series of templates designed to identify the types of relevant exploitation interests for each key exploitable result and from each partner’s perspective. It also presents a template to assess the value proposition offered by the project’s KERs to its main stakeholders as well as a template to identify and monitor publications with exploitation potential.

5.3.1 Individual exploitation interests per partner and KER

Partners may have varying interests with regards to the exploitation of the same result. For example, research institutes are more prone to have an interest on using a project result to conduct further research, while private entities are more likely to be interested in exploiting the same results for commercial purposes.

With the above in mind, the following template provides an illustrative overview of the individual exploitation pathways envisioned by each partner for each of the KERs. Through this template, the Exploitation Manager and consortium partners, collectively, can also obtain insights and spark discussions on where and how the consortium should focus towards the exploitation of each of the main project results.

	KER 1: Name	KER 2: Name	KER 3: Name	KER 4: Name	KER N: Name
	Exploitation interest/strategy				
Partner 1					
Partner 2					
Partner 3					

In each column, the relevant partner provides the exploitation interest for each KER, in consultation with the result owners to ensure that the planned exploitation is aligned with the access rights to the result. To represent the information in a readable yet clear manner, partners were asked to indicate their envisioned exploitation interests by choosing from a pre-determined list of relevant types of exploitation and entering the respective acronyms in each cell. Guidelines were provided to specify how each type of exploitation interest is represented by each acronym.

Commercial exploitation. Although varying, all the exploitation pathways listed below can be considered to fall under the ‘commercial exploitation’ category. They include potential exploitation interests of a project’s results (during or after the end of a project) that have a commercial objective: they ultimately aim to gain or increase profits and/or economic (i.e., market-related) competitiveness of the partner(s) that are to exploit them. We can classify the types of commercial exploitation pathways into three categories:

- **C(M):** Commercial interest in Making or improving a product with the ultimate goal to sell it.
- **C(L):** Commercial interest in Licensing the exploitable result (IP thereof) to third parties.
- **C(S):** Commercial interest in providing a Service, such as consultancy based on the ER or the knowledge built through it.

Internal product, service, or process development (I). The “Internal” exploitation type concerns exploitation approaches that will be used to improve an organisation’s internal processes and/or products of any kind. We envisage the following internal exploitation types:

- The improvement of certain internal processes/products/services in an organisation;
- The use project results to increase their existing portfolio and improve existing products or services; for instance, tailoring advisory services related to the Bioeconomy market etc.
- The use project results to enhance their knowledge and perform further research activities and/or leverage on them for pursuing further opportunities.

Further Research (R). The ‘research’ exploitation type concerns the exploitation approaches relevant for research activities that may not have a commercialisation potential but offer scientific exploitation of the ER. Through these types of exploitation, project partners aim to increase their

chances to access new research projects, to use them for future publications, or to be able to identify novel research concepts. We envisage the following research exploitation paths:

- Use of exploitable results (especially publications, research deliverables and general technical know-how) for ongoing and future projects and research schemes undertaken by university researchers and research centres.
- Use of exploitable results to advance research endeavours in the fields of Bioeconomy.

Standardisation (S). The outputs of projects may also be used in standardisation activities, potentially being useful to develop new standards and ultimately helping bridge the gap between research and development of new technologies and their large-scale market up-take and deployment.

Other. The “Other” exploitation category includes types that do not belong to the commercial, research and internal processes nor to standardisation activities. They may entail exploitation types related to civil or humanitarian purposes. Other purposes can be related to policy-making or advocacy. A further example are dissemination purposes, for example to increase awareness around sustainability standards/certifications. For the sake of this exercise, partners were asked to specify the concrete nature of the envisaged exploitation pathway when completing the template and selecting the “Other” category.

The list of categories was tailored to the most relevant uses identified for SUSTCERT4BIOBASED results, resulting in the following:

- **C(M)** – Commercial: Making or improving a product to sell it.
- **C(L)** – Commercial: Licensing it to third parties.
- **C(S)** – Commercial: Providing a service, such as consultancy.
- **I** – Internal use (e.g. using the ER to improve products or organizational processes).
- **R** – Research (e.g. in new research projects or internal R&D activities).
- **S** – Standardization activities
- **O** – Other types of exploitation (here, partners were requested to specify which specific use they were planning to give to the ER; for instance, pathways to derive value from the ER include dissemination or marketing activities).
 - **O(D).** This acronym refers to Other (Dissemination purposes). This category is the most relevant ‘other’ type of exploitation path for the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED (K)ERs. Therefore, to efficiently manage the space in the tables and enhance clarity, we also abbreviate it.

5.3.2 Individual post-project valorisation plans

To complement the individual exploitation plans of each project partner at the KER level, the table below allows partners to plot their plans for the post-project use of the overall outcomes of the project and the knowledge gained through its activities. Each partner is asked to identify the assets or outcomes of the project for which they hold the greater interest and to specify how they plan to, after the project, make (re-)use of them as well as of their general learnings.

Individual post-project valorisation plans		
Partner organization name	Project assets of major interest	Description
WHITE RESEARCH	Project website, deliverables	...

5.3.3 Value offered by the KERs to cover the needs of the project’s main stakeholders

Understanding how the project results cover the needs of the project’s target stakeholders can be very useful to support the definition of exploitation strategies as well as business models and business plans, which aim to maximise the value proposition of the project’s results. Therefore, the following table captures, in a structured way, the main needs of each target stakeholder group and, more importantly, how the different KERs contribute to deliver value to each of these stakeholders.

KER number	Key Exploitable Result (KER)	Target stakeholder(s)	Main stakeholder needs	Value proposition offered by the KER: how does it cover and deliver the identified needs

5.3.4 Exploitation plans and dissemination conditions for publications

Finally, the table below allows partners to define their exploitation interests for the publications that were drafted within the course of the project, in line with the project’s aim to disseminate scientific results in an open manner. Such publications often include multiple authors from different organisations, while the research presented in these works constitutes an IP item that is protected by the author’s copyright. While a comprehensive identification of publications is out of the scope of the present report, it is relevant for the Innovation Strategy to highlight those research outcomes for which partners attach an exploitation interest. This template also allows the consortium to track the status and progress of these publications. Importantly, it also allows authoring partners to monitor their compliance with open science requirements, helping ensure that the knowledge and data generated in the project are appropriately made accessible whenever required.

Type	Title	Author(s)	Publication/venue & year	Exploitation Interest	Main Partner(s)	Related ER#	Internal status	External status	Accessibility	Accessibility of data

6. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's Background and Exploitable Results

6.1 Overview of Background IP

The project partners identified the Background IP that is to be used in SUSTCERT4BIOBASED in order to carry out the project's activities and achieve its objectives. This identification, presented in the following table, was done at the beginning stages of the project and updated thereafter whenever necessary.

Table 2. Overview of Background IP

BG #	Description	Contributing partner(s)	Intended use in project and value (incl. WP)	Type of IP protection	Access rights: Conditions to use within the project*	Access rights: Conditions to use beyond the project*
BG1	Winery sustainability tool	CIRCE	This platform allows to monitor economic, technical and environmental KPIs specified for the wine sector, and its conclusions can be used to have a initial background for the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project	Copyright	Right for using the Background within the project, limited to specific activities in relation with the tool.	This Background will not be used for other uses than the project purposes, unless otherwise agreed under fair and reasonable conditions.
BG2	Know-how on environmental sustainability criteria	WFBR	This knowledge will be utilised in T1.2 in compilation of sustainability principles and criteria	Intangible asset / Experience	Right for using the Background within the project, limited to specific activities in relation with this knowledge	This Background will not be used for other uses than the project purposes, unless otherwise agreed under fair and reasonable conditions.
BG3	Know-how on range of biological resources	WFBR	This knowledge will be utilised in T1.1 in developing classification of biological resources	Intangible asset / Experience	Right for using the Background within the project, limited to specific activities in relation with the tool.	This Background will not be used for other uses than the project purposes, unless otherwise agreed under fair and reasonable conditions.
BG4	Overview of existing sustainability certification frameworks	ECOS	This information will be utilized in T1.3 in identifying relevant sustainability certification schemes/labels for biobased systems	Copyright	Right for using the Background within the project, limited to specific activities in relation with this knowledge	This Background will not be used for other uses than the project purposes, unless otherwise agreed under fair and reasonable conditions.

BG #	Description	Contributing partner(s)	Intended use in project and value (incl. WP)	Type of IP protection	Access rights: Conditions to use within the project*	Access rights: Conditions to use beyond the project*
BG5	Know-how on governance of certification schemes	WFBR + CU	This knowledge will be utilised in T1.2 in compilation of governance principles	Intangible asset / Experience	Right for using the Background within the project, limited to specific activities in relation with this knowledge	This Background will not be used for other uses than the project purposes, unless otherwise agreed under fair and reasonable conditions.
BG6	Biobased chemicals in EU economic classifications	WECR	This knowledge will be utilised in T1.1 in developing classification of biobased chemicals	Copyright	Right for using the Background within the project, limited to aggregated chemical application in relation with this knowledge	This Background will not be used for other uses than the project purposes, unless otherwise agreed under fair and reasonable conditions.
BG7	Biobased shares and biological feedstock conversion factors in C20 products	WECR	This knowledge will be utilised in T1.1 in developing classification of biobased chemicals	Copyright	Right for using the Background within the project, limited to aggregated chemical application in relation with this knowledge	This Background will not be used for other uses than the project purposes, unless otherwise agreed under fair and reasonable conditions.
BG8	Know-how on calculator platform	CIRCE	The expertise will be valuable to address relevant tasks having some assumptions and being faster in its advance	Intangible asset / Experience	Right for using the Background within the project, limited to specific activities in relation with this knowledge.	This Background will not be used for other uses than the project purposes, unless otherwise agreed under fair and reasonable conditions.
BG9	Tool to catalogue valorization solutions	CIRCE	The expertise will be valuable to address relevant tasks having some assumptions and being faster in its advance.	n/a	Right for using the Background within the project, limited to the	This Background will not be used for other uses than the project purposes, unless

BG #	Description	Contributing partner(s)	Intended use in project and value (incl. WP)	Type of IP protection	Access rights: Conditions to use within the project*	Access rights: Conditions to use beyond the project*
			This experience on previous tool will ease and make faster the selection of other licenses to work in the project.		specific activities in relation with the tool.	otherwise agreed under fair and reasonable conditions.
BG10	Experience in working with (large) data basis (PRODCOM, COMEXT)	WECR	This knowledge will be utilised in T2.2 in getting trade volumes of biobased chemical applications	Intangible asset / Experience	Right for using the Background within the project, limited to aggregated chemical application in relation with this knowledge	This Background will not be used for other uses than the project purposes, unless otherwise agreed under fair and reasonable conditions.
BG11	Experience in using econometric methods for analysing	WECR	This knowledge will be utilised in T2.4 in using gravity methods to understand effects of certification on trade	Intangible asset / Experience	Right for using the Background within the project, limited to specific activities in relation with this knowledge	This Background will not be used for other uses than the project purposes, unless otherwise agreed under fair and reasonable conditions.
BG12	Sustainability standard comparison tool	WFBR	This study will be used for inspiration in developing the monitoring tool in WP3	Copyright	Right for using the Background within the project, limited to specific activities in relation with this knowledge	This Background will not be used for other uses than the project purposes, unless otherwise agreed under fair and reasonable conditions.
BG13	Optimization of furnaces tool	CIRCE	This platforms allows to monitor different performance KPIs of baselines and innovations (economic, technical and environmental).	Not protected	Right for using the Background within the project, limited to specific activities in relation with the tool.	This Background will not be used for other uses than the project purposes, unless otherwise agreed under fair and reasonable conditions.

BG #	Description	Contributing partner(s)	Intended use in project and value (incl. WP)	Type of IP protection	Access rights: Conditions to use within the project*	Access rights: Conditions to use beyond the project*
BG14	Blueprint of sustainability certification schemes for bio-based products	ECOS	This information will be used as input in T3.2 when developing the monitoring tool	copyright	Right for using the Background within the project, limited to specific activities in relation with this knowledge	This Background will not be used for other uses than the project purposes, unless otherwise agreed under fair and reasonable conditions.
BG15	Know-how on Cost-benefit Analysis	WECR	The expertise will be valuable to address the Task 4.5 Quantification of costs and benefits of data from Task 4.4	Intangible asset / Experience	Right for using the Background within the project, limited to specific activities in relation with this knowledge	The background is not confidential and can be shared with externals
BG16	Knowledge of the policy framework related to bioeconomy	ECOS	This document provides background on how the relationship between policies and private VSS should operate and therefore will be used as background when developing tailored policy recommendations	copyright	Right for using the Background within the project, limited to specific activities in relation with this knowledge	This Background will not be used for other uses than the project purposes, unless otherwise agreed under fair and reasonable conditions.
BG17	Bioeconomy Strategy Accelerator Toolkit	CIRCE	This is an online platform acting as a repository to provide information to guide decisions-makers and stakeholders. This information help`s policy makers to develop their regional bioeconomy strategy. The toolkit contributes to	Open Access	Rights for using the Background within the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project.	This Background is available in open access for its exploitation in http://bioeconomy-strategy-toolkit.eu/

BG #	Description	Contributing partner(s)	Intended use in project and value (incl. WP)	Type of IP protection	Access rights: Conditions to use within the project*	Access rights: Conditions to use beyond the project*
			identifying specific regional assets, gaps, weaknesses. Also, it provides tips on how to develop or strengthen its own regional bioeconomy strategy. Available in http://bioeconomy-strategy-toolkit.eu/			
BG18	Know how on website content development and management	WHITE	This knowledge will be used in order to develop the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED website	Intangible asset / Experience	free to use	This Background will not be used for other uses than the project purposes

6.2 Identified (Key) Exploitable Results

This section presents all the Exploitable Results (ERs) developed in the context of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED, as identified by the consortium. After internal prioritisation discussions, we classified these results between Key Exploitation Results (KERs) and partial or secondary ERs. They will be identified and defined in order to provide a basis for subsequent discussions in this report, which will build on these results to discuss the exploitation and valorisation strategies of the project and its consortium partners.

These project ERs are built upon the data, knowledge and assets both (i) brought to the project by project partners and (ii) developed throughout the course of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's activities.

Since projects are prone to produce a large number of ERs, it is most sensible to conduct a prioritisation among the identified results. In order to pave the way for post-project exploitation and maximise the project's impact while also making an efficient use of the resources of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's exploitation management task, we focus the project's exploitation plan on the results that hold the greatest exploitation potential, impact and added value for the consortium partners as well as the project's stakeholders.

In this context, it was concluded that the KERs of the project are the ones identified in the table below. Therefore, they will be the focus when designing the post-project exploitation strategies that are required for: (i) maximising SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's value propositions to the main target stakeholders groups; (ii) ensuring the sustainability of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED work beyond the project; and (iii) helping consortium partners envision individual or joint realistic strategies to valorise their innovations in their preferred way (e.g., in the market, in future research activities, through reputation building, via internal product development, etc.).

6.2.1 Key Exploitable Results (KERs) of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED

The KERs of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED were identified and validated by the consortium partners. In Table 3 below, we provide a description of each KER, together with the corresponding project WP under which they were created, and the partial or secondary ERs of which they are comprised or on which they rely (see Table 4 for the descriptions of the rest of the project's identified ERs).

Table 3. Key Exploitable Results

KER Name	Description	ERs included	Related project activities
Classification of biological resources and biobased products	Classification of all existing biological resources and of the existing biobased products within the most relevant industrial sectors of the European bioeconomy. Biological resources are categorized into four main types and 22 sub-categories based on source and type. Biobased products are classified by industrial sectors such as construction, textiles, and chemicals, using NACE codes and PRODCOM subcategories. The report identifies biobased product groups already in commercial use and highlights potential biobased value chains and relevant feedstocks for each sector.	ER1	WP1
Catalogue of sustainability certification schemes and labels for industrial biobased systems	11 Factsheets were created to provide an overview of sustainability certification schemes and labels for industrial biobased systems. These factsheets cover general information, governance, and sustainability principles. The goal is to increase awareness and promote the adoption of sustainability schemes for biobased products, aiding actors in selecting suitable schemes for their value chains and organisations.	ER3	WP1

KER Name	Description	ERs included	Related project activities
Identification of the most representative biobased value chains in the EU	This study used Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) to rank 18 selected biobased value chains within six industrial sectors, evaluating them against 11 sub-criteria under three main criteria. The goal was to identify which value chains are most market-implemented, can transition from fossil-based products, and enhance overall sustainability in line with EU objectives.	ER5	WP2
Quantification of global trade flows of selected biobased value chains	Database of trade volumes for biological resources and biobased product. An excel file that includes detailed production and trade flow data for certified and non-certified products across ten selected biobased value chains. The main activity involved mapping, combining, and harmonizing product definitions and codes from various statistical sources.	ER6	WP2
BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring tool	BMT for assessment of effective, robustness, and comprehensiveness of existing sustainability certification schemes and labels for industrial biobased systems - Joint deliverable/asset of the BIOBASEDCERT cluster	ER9	WP3
Results from testing of the BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool on selected certification schemes and labels	Results from testing the developed monitoring tool on selected sustainability certifications schemes and labels for biobased systems	ER10	WP3
Methodology for cost benefit analysis and internalizing of externalities for sustainability certification	An inventory of relevant methodologies to assess cost and benefit analysis (CBA) including internalizing externalities	ER11	WP4
Data collection template for cost and benefit analysis	Data collection template for carrying out cost-benefit analysis based on methodology defined in T4.1	ER13	WP4
Recommendations to policy makers	Two policy briefs targeting policy makers - Joint deliverables of the BIOBASEDCERT cluster	ER16	WP5
Recommendations to standards writers, scheme owners and certification bodies	Thematic briefs laying down recommendations to scheme/label owners and standardization bodies	ER17	WP5
Recommendations to industrial biobased value chain actors	Thematic briefs to industrial biobased value chain actors	ER18	WP5
Recommendations to regional bioeconomy actors	Thematic briefs to regional bioeconomy actors	ER19	WP5

6.2.2 All Exploitable Results (ERs) of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED

Here, we provide a list of all the identified ERs that were generated within the project's activities. These ERs are presented in the table that follows, along with their description and the corresponding tasks or WPs under which they will be created.

Table 4. SUSTCER4BIOBASED Exploitable Results (ERs)

ER nr. and Name	Description	Related project activities
ER1: Classification of biological resources and biobased products	Classification of all existing biological resources and of the existing biobased products within the most relevant industrial sectors of the European bioeconomy. Biological resources are categorized into four main types and 22 sub-categories based on source and type. Biobased products are classified by industrial sectors such as construction, textiles, and chemicals, using NACE codes and PRODCOM subcategories. The report identifies biobased product groups already in commercial use and highlights potential biobased value chains and relevant feedstocks for each sector.	WP1
ER2: Compilation of sustainability principles and criteria	Compilation of sustainability principles and criteria from review of relevant legislation, standards, schemes and studies	WP1
ER3: Catalogue of sustainability certification schemes and labels for industrial biobased systems	11 Factsheets were created to provide an overview of sustainability certification schemes and labels for industrial biobased systems. These factsheets cover general information, governance, and sustainability principles. The goal is to increase awareness and promote the adoption of sustainability schemes for biobased products, aiding actors in selecting suitable schemes for their value chains and organisations.	WP1
ER4: Analysis of synergies and trade-offs	A range of sustainability targets from the seventeen Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) defined by the United Nations were selected with a focus on four main sustainability dimensions (Environmental, Circularity, Social, and Economic). The analysis of the SDG targets against the sustainability dimensions allowed the identification of the most relevant SDG targets for sustainability requirements defined in this project scope.	WP1
ER5: Identification of the most representative biobased value chains in the EU	This study used Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) to rank 18 selected biobased value chains within six industrial sectors, evaluating them against 11 sub-criteria under three main criteria. The goal was to identify which value chains are most market-implemented, can transition from fossil-based products, and enhance overall sustainability in line with EU objectives.	WP2
ER6: Quantification of global trade flows of selected biobased value chains	Database of trade volumes for biological resources and biobased product. An excel file that includes detailed production and trade flow data for certified and non-certified products across ten selected biobased value chains. The main activity involved mapping, combining, and harmonizing product definitions and codes from various statistical sources.	WP2
ER7: Analysis of effects of certification on EU trade of biobased value chains	Report investigating the relation between certification and traded volumes of bio-based products along the relevant value chains and sets the basis for future econometric analysis of trade flows of bio-based products and their raw feedstocks	WP2
"ER8: Review of existing monitoring approaches for schemes and labels"	In-depth review of existing guidelines, assessment tools, benchmarks, evaluations, and legislations ("tools") that assess sustainability certification schemes and labels.	WP3
ER9: BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring system	BMT for assessment of effective, robustness, and comprehensiveness of existing sustainability certification schemes and labels for industrial	WP3

ER nr. and Name	Description	Related project activities
	biobased systems - Joint deliverable/asset of the BIOBASEDCERT cluster	
ER10: Results from testing of the BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool on selected certification schemes and labels	Results from testing the developed monitoring tool on selected sustainability certifications schemes and labels for biobased systems	WP3
ER11: Methodology for cost benefit analysis and internalizing of externalities for sustainability certification	An inventory of relevant methodologies to assess cost and benefit analysis (CBA) including internalizing externalities	WP4
ER12: Selection of biobased value chains for cost benefit analysis	Selection of three industrial biobased value chains for further in-depth evaluation of the costs and benefits of adoption of sustainability schemes and labels in these three chains	WP4
ER13: Data collection template for cost and benefit analysis	Data collection template for carrying out cost-benefit analysis based on methodology defined in T4.1	WP4
ER14: Cost benefit analysis for the selected biobased value chains and feasibility analysis	Carrying out CBA and feasibility analysis for the 3 selected biobased value chains	WP4
ER15: Synthesis of findings	Synthesis of findings from the project and categorization of recommendations in terms of targeted stakeholders	WP5
ER16: Recommendations to policy makers	Two policy briefs targeting policy makers - Joint deliverables of the BIOBASEDCERT cluster	WP5
ER17: Recommendations to standards writers, scheme owners and certification bodies	Thematic briefs laying down recommendations to scheme/label owners and standardization bodies	WP5
ER18: Recommendations to industrial biobased value chain actors	Thematic briefs to industrial biobased value chain actors	WP5
ER19: Recommendations to regional bioeconomy actors	Thematic briefs to regional bioeconomy actors	WP5
ER20: SUSTCERT4BIOBASED website	Website to present and promote the project and its results	WP6
ER21: Creating a Network of Interest related to the project and its results	Engaging more than 50 stakeholders and support the knowledge exchange around the sector	WP6

7. IPR Management and Exploitation Plans for SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's Results

Building upon the partner input gathered through the templates of section 5 and the KERs defined in the previous section, the present section delves into IPR ownership and management procedures, such as protection, the definition of access rights and exploitation interests and pathways. The information presented in Table 5 arose from an iterative process that comprised multiple rounds of review and validation from partners.

To assign ownership to each KER, a starting point was the identified role and contribution of each partner to the realisation of each project activity. From that, partners expressed ownership claims, which were collectively reviewed and validated. This process allows for the proactive identification of potential conflicts related to the ownership of the IPR behind key exploitable results.

In addition, based on the templates developed by the Innovation manager, all partners were then invited to express and elaborate on their exploitation interest, by describing the type of their exploitation interest and respective pathway for each specific project result, during and/or after the end of the project. Additionally, the templates allowed to collect important input regarding the actions and responsibilities each partner foresees for the protection of the IPR within the KERs. At the same time, it helped the Exploitation manager to spot early on inconsistencies or unforeseen claims from specific partners over some results, to consult partners bilaterally and collect a proper justification about the claim. In that way, potential IP conflicts were identified and solved timely.

7.1 KER

KER #1: Classification of biological resources and biobased products			
Developing partners	CIRCE, WFBR	Related BG	BG3, BG6, BG7
Owner(s)	CIRCE	Joint ownership share allocation	N/A
Chosen IPR protection mechanism	Copyrights	Chosen jurisdiction for registration and geographical coverage	Belgium, Global
Conditions for use	CC BY-NC-SA		
Conditions for dissemination and exploitation	Open for non-commercial use by all stakeholders		
Exploitation interests and potential	Utilise this classification in new projects, actively promote it both within and beyond the organization, and enhance awareness to encourage broader adoption		

KER #2: Catalogue of sustainability certification schemes and labels for industrial biobased systems			
Developing partners	WFBR, CIRCE, CU	Related BG	BG4
Owner(s)	WFBR	Joint ownership share allocation	N/A

Chosen IPR protection mechanism	Copyright	Chosen jurisdiction for registration and geographical coverage	Belgium, Global
Conditions for use	CC BY-NC-SA		
Conditions for dissemination and exploitation	Open for non-commercial use by all stakeholders		
Exploitation interests and potential	Host the factsheets on the project website to enhance visibility and actively promote them during engagements with industrial stakeholders.		

KER #3: Identification of the most representative biobased value chains in the EU

Developing partners	CIRCE, WR,CU	Related BG	N/A
Owner(s)	CIRCE	Joint ownership share allocation	N/A
Chosen IPR protection mechanism	Copyright	Chosen jurisdiction for registration and geographical coverage	Belgium, Global
Conditions for use	CC BY-NC-SA		
Conditions for dissemination and exploitation	Open for non-commercial use by all stakeholders		
Exploitation interests and potential	Share the results obtained with public bodies and policy makers so that they can take advantage of the information for future decision-making.		

KER #4: Quantification of global trade flows of selected biobased value chains

Developing partners	WR, CIRCE, CU	Related BG	BG10,BG11
Owner(s)	WECR	Joint ownership share allocation	N/A
Chosen IPR protection mechanism	Copyright	Chosen jurisdiction for registration and geographical coverage	Belgium, Global
Conditions for use	CC BY-NC-SA		
Conditions for dissemination and exploitation	Open for non-commercial use by all stakeholders		
Exploitation interests and potential	Present findings to industry stakeholders and policymakers on the current status of the trade that could serve as a reference for future development of trade and certification of biobased value chains.		

KER #5: BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool

Developing partners	BIOBASEDCERT cluster	Related BG	BG1,BG12, BG14
Owner(s)	WFBR, ECOS, UU, TUB	Joint ownership share allocation	YES (Agreement)
Chosen IPR protection mechanism	Copyright	Chosen jurisdiction for registration and geographical coverage	Belgium, Global
Conditions for use	CC BY-NC-SA		
Conditions for dissemination and exploitation	Open for non-commercial use by all stakeholders		
Exploitation interests and potential	Encourage the adoption of BMT by scheme owners as a self-assessment tool and facilitate their integration into ongoing standardization efforts to drive industry-wide alignment and best practices. Also, for EU policy makers to use it as a co-regulation instrument.		

KER #6: Results from testing of the BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool on selected certification schemes and labels

Developing partners	WR, ECOS, CU	Related BG	N/A
Owner(s)	WFBR	Joint ownership share allocation	N/A
Chosen IPR protection mechanism	Copyright	Chosen jurisdiction for registration and geographical coverage	Belgium, Global
Conditions for use	CC BY-NC-SA		
Conditions for dissemination and exploitation	Open for non-commercial use by all stakeholders		
Exploitation interests and potential	Share the results from the testing with the CSL owners involved so that they can utilize in further improvement of their standards		

KER #7: Methodology for cost benefit analysis and internalizing of externalities for sustainability certification

Developing partners	WR, CU	Related BG	BG15
Owner(s)	WEcR	Joint ownership share allocation	N/A
Chosen IPR protection mechanism	Copyright	Chosen jurisdiction for registration and geographical coverage	Belgium, Global

Conditions for use	CC BY-NC-SA
Conditions for dissemination and exploitation	Open for non-commercial use by all stakeholders
Exploitation interests and potential	Publish methodology in academic journals, present at conferences, and promote its application for assessment of feasibility including externalities.

KER #8: Data collection template for cost and benefit analysis

Developing partners	CU, WR	Related BG	N/A
Owner(s)	CU	Joint ownership share allocation	N/A
Chosen IPR protection mechanism	Copyright	Chosen jurisdiction for registration and geographical coverage	Belgium, Global
Conditions for use	CC BY-NC-SA		
Conditions for dissemination and exploitation	Open for non-commercial use by all stakeholders		
Exploitation interests and potential	Make the template freely available to the public, ensuring broad access and encouraging its use and adaptation to make cost and benefit analysis for other value chains beyond the project.		

KER #9: Recommendations to policy makers

Developing partners	BIOBASEDCERT cluster	Related BG	BG16,BG17
Owner(s)	WFBR and ECOS, SQ Consult, TU Berlin	Joint ownership share allocation	YES
Chosen IPR protection mechanism	Copyright	Chosen jurisdiction for registration and geographical coverage	Belgium, Global
Conditions for use	CC BY-NC-SA		
Conditions for dissemination and exploitation	Open for non-commercial use by all stakeholders		
Exploitation interests and potential	Share the results obtained with policy makers so that they can take advantage of the information for future decision-making.		

KER #10: Recommendations to standards writers, scheme owners and certification bodies

Developing partners	ECOS, WR	Related BG	N/A
Owner(s)	ECOS	Joint ownership share allocation	N/A
Chosen IPR protection mechanism	Copyright	Chosen jurisdiction for registration and geographical coverage	Belgium, Global
Conditions for use	CC BY-NC-SA		
Conditions for dissemination and exploitation	Open for non-commercial use by all stakeholders		
Exploitation interests and potential	Share the results obtained with scheme owners and standardization bodies so that they can take advantage of the information for future decision-making.		

KER #11: Recommendations to industrial biobased value chain actors

Developing partners	CIRCE, ECOS, WR	Related BG	N/A
Owner(s)	CIRCE	Joint ownership share allocation	N/A
Chosen IPR protection mechanism	Copyright	Chosen jurisdiction for registration and geographical coverage	Belgium, Global
Conditions for use	CC BY-NC-SA		
Conditions for dissemination and exploitation	Open for non-commercial use by all stakeholders		
Exploitation interests and potential	Share the results obtained with industrial biobased value chain actors so that they can take advantage of the information for future decision-making.		

KER #12: Recommendations to regional bioeconomy actors

Developing partners	CIRCE, ECOS, WR	Related BG	BG17
Owner(s)	CIRCE	Joint ownership share allocation	N/A
Chosen IPR protection mechanism	Copyright	Chosen jurisdiction for registration and geographical coverage	Belgium, Global
Conditions for use	CC BY-NC-SA		

Conditions for dissemination and exploitation	Open for non-commercial use by all stakeholders
Exploitation interests and potential	Disseminate the results to regional bioeconomy stakeholders, enabling them to leverage the information for informed decision-making in future initiatives

Having identified the right owners and protection measures for each of the project’s results, the following table identifies the most relevant, immediate post-project actions that will be necessary to ensure that such protection is achieved and that the subsequent exploitation of the results is enabled.

Therefore, the table below presents a simplified roadmap with the most crucial actions to ensure the exploitation readiness of the KER.

Table 5. KER's exploitation roadmap

ER number	Key Exploitable Result (KER)	Action type	Action's description	Estimated costs (outside project budget)	Responsible partner(s)	Timeline
KER1	Classification of biological resources and biobased products	Exploitation	Use this classification in new projects, present it within and outside the organization to inform about it and increase its use by others	N/A	CIRCE, WFBR	To be valorised in follow-up research and industry collaborations for at least 5 years.
KER2	Catalogue of sustainability certification schemes and labels for industrial biobased systems	Exploitation	Placing the factsheets in project website to increase visibility, informing about them during engagement with industrial stakeholders	N/A	WR- WFBR	To be valorised in follow-up research and industry collaborations for at least 5 years.
KER3	Identification of the most representative biobased value chains in the EU	Exploitation	Share the results obtained with public bodies and policy makers so that they can take advantage of the information for future decision-making.	N/A	CIRCE	Facilitate integration into policy dialogues and valorise in new EU-funded projects for at least 5 years.
KER4	Quantification of global trade flows of selected biobased value chains	Dissemination & Policy Uptake	Present findings to industry stakeholders and policymakers on the current status of the trade that could serve as a reference for future development of trade and certification of biobased value chain	N/A	WR- WEcR	To be valorised in further research, trade reports, and policy discussions for at least 5 years.
KER5	BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool	Exploitation & Standardization	Encourage the adoption of BMT by scheme owners as a self-assessment tool and facilitate their integration into ongoing standardization efforts to drive industry-wide alignment and best	N/A	WR- WFBR, ECOS, UU, TUB	HARMONITOR Project: A PhD student from Utrecht University is expected to take over the further development of the Outcome level, supporting its continued

ER number	Key Exploitable Result (KER)	Action type	Action's description	Estimated costs (outside project budget)	Responsible partner(s)	Timeline
			practices. Also, for EU policy makers to use it as a co-regulation instrument..			<p>development within an academic framework.</p> <p>STAR4BBS Project: The project has expressed intentions to further develop the System level and also develop a web-based BMT tool incorporated into their website.</p> <p>SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Project: Through the involvement of the project's coordinator, who is a member of the CEN Technical Committee TC 411 Biobased products, Working group WG4 on sustainability, facilitate integration of BMT content level sustainability criteria into relevant standard updates.</p>
KER6	Results from testing of the BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool on selected certification schemes and labels	Exploitation	Share the results from the testing with the CSL owners involved so that they can utilize in further improvement of their standards	N/A	WR- WFBR	The assessment results shared with the tested CSLs will facilitate update of their standards over the following 5 years.
KER7	Methodology for cost benefit analysis and internalizing of externalities for	Dissemination & Exploitation	Publish methodology in academic journals, present at conferences, and promote its application for assessment of feasibility including externalities.	N/A	WR- WEcR	The methodology developed will be further valorized and developed in new projects by the experts or other researchers over the following 5 years.

ER number	Key Exploitable Result (KER)	Action type	Action's description	Estimated costs (outside project budget)	Responsible partner(s)	Timeline
	sustainability certification					
KER8	Data collection template for cost and benefit analysis	Exploitation	Make the template publicly available	N/A	CU	The template developed will facilitate cost benefit assessment of other value chains beyond our project. It will be freely accessible and usable through Zenodo.
KER9	Recommendations to policy makers	Dissemination & Policy Uptake	Share the results obtained with policy makers so that they can take advantage of the information for future decision-making.	N/A	WR-WFBR, ECOS, SQ Consult, TU Berlin	The recommendations are publicly available on the project website (active for another 4 years after the end of the project) and can be accessed by stakeholders and decision-makers for ongoing reference and uptake
KER10	Recommendations to standards writers, scheme owners and certification bodies	Dissemination & Exploitation	Share the results obtained with scheme owners and standardization bodies so that they can take advantage of the information for future decision-making.	N/A	ECOS	The recommendations are publicly available on the project website (active for another 4 years after the end of the project) and can be accessed by stakeholders and decision-makers for ongoing reference and uptake
KER11	Recommendations to industrial biobased value chain actors	Dissemination & Exploitation	Share the results obtained with industrial biobased value chain actors so that they can take advantage of the information for future decision-making.	N/A	CIRCE	The recommendations are publicly available on the project website (active for another 4 years after the end of the project) and can be accessed by stakeholders and decision-makers for ongoing reference and uptake

ER number	Key Exploitable Result (KER)	Action type	Action's description	Estimated costs (outside project budget)	Responsible partner(s)	Timeline
KER12	Recommendations to regional bioeconomy actors	Dissemination & Exploitation	Share the results obtained with regional bioeconomy actors so that they can take advantage of the information for future decision-making.	N/A	CIRCE	The recommendations are publicly available on the project website (active for another 4 years after the end of the project) and can be accessed by stakeholders and decision-makers for ongoing reference and uptake

7.1.1 Joint Ownership Agreement

BIOBASEDCERT Cluster

BIOBASEDCERT Cluster is a collaboration between three Horizon Europe projects—SUSTCERT4BIOBASED, STAR4BBS, and HARMONITOR—working to enhance sustainability certification for bio-based systems. The cluster aims to provide a comprehensive overview of existing certification schemes and labels, analyze global trade data to differentiate certified and uncertified bio-based materials, assess the feasibility of selected certification schemes, and promote the adoption of effective sustainability standards among stakeholders. Through joint initiatives, including the development of the BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool (BMT), the cluster contributes to harmonizing certification practices and advancing the sustainability of bio-based value chains.

Figure 2. BIOBASEDCERT Cluster

The three projects collaborated closely to engage various target stakeholders, co-organising numerous events and supporting each other in dissemination efforts. Additionally, they joined forces to develop the BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool (BMT), the most significant asset of the projects. Beyond the BMT, the projects also worked together to co-draft policy briefs.

The BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool (BMT)

The BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool (BMT) is a comprehensive framework designed to help the European Commission and certification scheme and label (CSL) owners assess the effectiveness and robustness of sustainability certification in bio-based systems. By evaluating how existing CSLs align with EU sustainability policies and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), the BMT aims to increase transparency and support the harmonisation of certification schemes. It provides insights into the strengths and weaknesses of current schemes, helping policymakers and scheme owners improve their standards and governance. The tool, structured in three levels (System, Content, and Outcome), uses a set of standardized indicators to measure the impact of CSLs and will **be available as a publicly accessible Excel-based tool**. In addition, a web-based version of the monitoring tool will be available. The first demo can be found already [here](#). Once the demo will be tested, a link on our website will redirect users to the online version of the BMT (hosted in STAR4BBS website).

Figure 3. BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool levels

The development of the BMT is a collaborative effort between the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED, STAR4BBS, and HARMONITOR projects, ensuring that expertise from all three initiatives is integrated. Each project leads one of the three monitoring levels, contributing its specialized

knowledge while ensuring a harmonized and well-rounded approach. By working together, the projects reduce duplication, streamlined stakeholder engagement, and enhanced the credibility of the tool. The BMT was further tested and refined through pilot audits and consultations with stakeholders, ensuring its applicability across diverse bio-based value chains.

Joint Ownership Agreement

Since one of the main assets of the project, the BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool (BMT), was co-developed by all three projects, it was essential to discuss its long-term sustainability, exploitation, and ownership beyond the project's duration. Several discussions took place between the coordinators and exploitation managers of the sister projects to establish clear agreements on these matters.

WHITE took the initiative to draft a Co-ownership Agreement that could be used by all three projects. After conducting internal consultations with SUSTCERT4BIOBASED partners, WHITE shared the draft with the BIOBASEDCERT Cluster for further discussion. To gain additional expert guidance, WHITE also applied for Horizon Results Booster Module C and was

Figure 4. Co-ownership Agreement and Horizon Results Booster

assigned an expert mentor specializing in joint ownership and exploitation strategies. The agreement and key ownership issues were shared with the mentor, who provided valuable feedback. Following multiple consultations between the three projects and the mentor, a final Co-ownership Agreement was prepared by all relevant parties, securing the future use and exploitation of the co-developed assets, particularly the BMT, which holds the highest potential for long-term impact.

Intentions for continuation

The following outlines the anticipated continuation and further development of the BMT, based on preliminary discussions with relevant projects and stakeholders. These plans are indicative in nature and do not represent binding commitments:

- **HARMONITOR Project:** A PhD student from Utrecht University is expected to take over the further development of the Outcome level, supporting its continued development within an academic framework.
- **STAR4BBS Project:** The project has expressed intentions to further develop the System level of the Tool. Also development of the BMT web-based version incorporated into their website.
- **SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Project:** Through the involvement of the project's coordinator, who is a member of the CEN Technical Committee TC 411 Biobased products, Working group WG4 on sustainability, facilitate integration of BMT content level sustainability criteria into relevant standard updates.

These plans reflect current intentions and may evolve based on project priorities, available resources, and emerging opportunities.

The draft Agreement can be found annexed in this document in Annex I.

Jointly developed assets for the BIOBASEDCERT Cluster

The table below presents the joint assets developed by the BIOBASEDCERT Cluster:

Table 6. BIOBASEDCERT Jointly-owned IPT¹

Jointly-owned IP (e.g., KER #)	Allocation of shares among joint owners	Terms for post-project ownership, IPR transfer, etc.	IP protection and maintenance responsibilities	IP monitoring and enforcement responsibilities	Governing jurisdiction and dispute resolution
<p>KER 5: BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool</p>	<p>33% SUSTCERT4BIOBASED (50 % WFBR, 50% ECOS), 33% STAR4BBS (100% TU Berlin), HARMONITOR (100% UU)</p>	<p>The parties agree to rely on copyrights and specifically CC BY-NC-SA. The Partners shall jointly manage the Assets. Any significant decisions regarding the management of the Assets must be approved by 2/3 majority of the Partners.</p>	<p>(a) All costs resulting from the IP application, protection and monitoring shall be borne by the Partners in proportion to their respective shares of the relevant Result. (b) Any necessary financial contributions towards the development, maintenance, and protection of the Assets shall be shared based on the division ownership by the Partners.</p>	<p>(a) The Parties that co-own a result may appoint one of them (“Managing Partner”) to oversee the protection, filing and prosecution of the relevant Intellectual Property Right. The Managing Partner may prepare, file, and prosecute applications regarding the Intellectual Property Right of the Asset after consulting with the other Parties in good faith. (b) Each Partner shall inform the other Partners promptly of any infringement or suspected or threatened infringement of the Result of which it becomes aware, and the Partners shall promptly consult with each other in good faith with a view to reaching agreement on the action to be taken in respect of the infringement in question. A decision on the</p>	<p>This Agreement shall be governed by Belgian law. In the event of any dispute related to this Agreement, the Partners shall first seek to negotiate and resolve the dispute amicably under principles of good faith. If an amicable settlement cannot be reached, the dispute shall be referred to professional mediation in accordance with Belgian arbitration rules. Should negotiation or mediation fail to resolve the dispute, legal proceedings shall be submitted to the jurisdiction of the Belgian courts.</p>

¹ **Disclaimer:** The details provided here are currently under discussion as part of the co-ownership agreement and may be subject to change.

Jointly-owned IP (e.g., KER #)	Allocation of shares among joint owners	Terms for post-project ownership, IPR transfer, etc.	IP protection and maintenance responsibilities	IP monitoring and enforcement responsibilities	Governing jurisdiction and dispute resolution
				action must be approved by 2/3 majority of the Partners.	
KER 9: Joint policy brief	<p>33% SUSTCERT4BIOBASED (50 % WFBR, 50% ECOS), 33% STAR4BBS (100% TU Berlin), 33% HARMONITOR (100% SQ Consult)</p>	<p>The parties agree to rely on copyrights and specifically CC BY-NC-SA.</p>	n/a	n/a	n/a

7.2 Publications

Within the course of project, high-quality scientific works were submitted, in line with the project's aim to disseminate scientific results in an open manner. In the table below, the consortium has identified the following relevant publications and deliverables, which were published within the course and context of the project. **All of the project's public deliverables are also uploaded to Zenodo.**

All public deliverables will be uploaded to the website and Zenodo after the official approval by the commission.

Table 7. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Publications

Type	Title	Author(s)	Name of publication/venue & year	Exploitation Interest	Main Partner(s)	Accessibility	Accessibility of data
Article in journal	Assessment of EU Bio-Based Economy Sectors Based on Environmental, Socioeconomic, and Technical Indicators	Víctor Fernández Ocamica, Monique Bernardes Figueirêdo, Sebastián Zapata, Carmen Bartolomé	Sustainability, 2024	Research	CIRCE	Open access	here
Article in journal	Trade-offs and Synergies of Key Biobased Value Chains and Sustainability	Víctor Fernández Ocamica, Bárbara Palacino, Carmen Bartolomé, Monique Bernardes Figueirêdo, Cristina Lázaro García	Sustainability, 2025	Research	CIRCE	Open access	here
Publication in conference proceedings	Unveiling the True Value: Exploring Costs and Benefits of Sustainable Certification Schemes in the Biopolyethylene Value Chain	Aramyan, L., Vissers, L., Manouchehrabadi, B., Niemenoja, K., Verwijst, L.	Proceedings of 32 nd EUBCE 2024	Research	WEcR,CU	Open access	here

Type	Title	Author(s)	Name of publication/venue & year	Exploitation Interest	Main Partner(s)	Accessibility	Accessibility of data
Publication in conference proceedings	A System to Assess and Monitor the Sustainability Performance of Existing Sustainability Certification Schemes for Biobased Systems	Balleman, H., Vural Gursel, I., Väyrynen, L., Waite, M., Crepy, M.	Proceedings of 32 nd EUBCE 2024	Research	WFBR and ECOS	Open access	here
Publication in conference proceedings	Methodology for the Socio-environmental and Socio-economic Analysis of the EU Bio-based Industry	Fernández Ocamica, V., Bernardes Figueirêdo, M., Bartolomé, C.	Proceedings of 32 nd EUBCE 2024	Research	CIRCE	Open access	here
Publication in conference proceedings	Towards Comprehensive Cost-Benefit Analysis: Incorporating Externalities in Sustainability Certification for Biobased Products.	Aramyan, L., Vissers, L., Wang, S., Niemenoja, K., Verwijst, L.	Proceedings of 33 rd EUBCE 2025	Research	WEcR	Open access	Not yet
Publication in conference proceedings	BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring System Content level for the assessment of the sustainability certification schemes for biobased systems	Vural Gursel, I., Balleman, H., Väyrynen, L.	Proceedings of 33 rd EUBCE 2025	Research	WFBR and ECOS	Open access	Not yet
Deliverable	D1.1 Classification of biological resources and biobased products	Bárbara Palacino, Monique Bernardes Figueirêdo, Cristina Lazaro	Oct-22	Research	CIRCE	Open access	here
Deliverable	D1.2 Catalogue of sustainability certification schemes and labels	Iris Vural Gursel, Heike Axmann, Lesly Garcia Chavez and Marta Rodríguez Illera	Apr-23	Research	WFBR	Open access	here

Type	Title	Author(s)	Name of publication/venue & year	Exploitation Interest	Main Partner(s)	Accessibility	Accessibility of data
Deliverable	D1.3 Analysis of synergies and trade-offs	Bárbara Palacino, Monique Bernardes Figueirêdo, Cristina Lazaro	Apr-23	Research	CIRCE	Open access	here
Deliverable	D2.1 Identification of the most representative biobased value chains	Víctor Fernández Ocamica , Sebastian Zapata Habas, Cristina Lázaro and Monique Bernardes Figueirêdo	Apr-23	Research	CIRCE	Open access	here
Deliverable	D2.2 Database of trade volumes for biological resources and biobased products	Myrna van Leeuwen, Bobby Tsvetkov, Frans Godeschalk, David Verhoog	Nov-23	Research	WEcR	Open access	here
Deliverable	D2.3 Analysis of effects of certification on EU trade of biobased value chains	Ana Gonzalez-Martinez, Myrna van Leeuwen	Nov-23	Research	WEcR	Open access	here
Deliverable	D3.1 Review of existing monitoring approaches for schemes and labels	Mariana López Dávila	Nov-22	Research	ECOS	Open access	here
Deliverable	D4.1 Review of methodologies for cost benefit analysis and internalizing externalities for sustainability certification	Lusine Aramyan, Irina Verweij-Novikova, Luuk Vissers (WR-WEcR), Loek Verwijst (CU)	Apr-23	Research	WEcR, CU	Open access	here

Type	Title	Author(s)	Name of publication/venue & year	Exploitation Interest	Main Partner(s)	Accessibility	Accessibility of data
Deliverable	D4.2 Selection of biobased value chains for cost benefit analysis	Lusine Aramyan, Irina Verweij-Novikova, Luuk Vissers (WR-WEER), Loek Verwijst (CU)	Apr-23	Research	WEeR, CU	Open access	here
Deliverable	D5.2 Mid-term Policy Brief of the BIOBASEDCERT Project Cluster	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED: Iris Vural Gursel (WR); Marxine Waite, Laura Vayrynen (ECOS) HARMONITOR: Sergio Ugarte (SQ Consult). STAR4BBS: Luana Ladu, Nikola Matovik (Technical University of Berlin).	Nov- 23	Research	WR, ECOS/ SQ Consult /TU Berlin	Open access	here
Deliverable	D3.2 Evaluation of existing schemes and labels	Iris Vural Gursel, Heleen Ballemans, Heike Axmann, Lesly Garcia Chavez and Marta Rodríguez-Illera	To be uploaded upon acceptance	Research	WFBR	Open access	It will be accessible via our website
Deliverable	D3.3. Description of the monitoring system	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED: Iris Vural Gursel (WR); Laura Vayrynen (ECOS) HARMONITOR: Maulidia Khairani, Li Shen, Martin Junginger (UU)	To be uploaded upon acceptance	Research	ECOS , WR/ UU/ TU Berlin	Open access	It will be accessible via our website

Type	Title	Author(s)	Name of publication/venue & year	Exploitation Interest	Main Partner(s)	Accessibility	Accessibility of data
		STAR4BBS: Luana Ladu, Nikola Matovik (Technical University of Berlin).					
Deliverable	D4.3. Data collection template for cost benefit analysis	Karolina Niemenoja	To be uploaded upon acceptance	Research	CU	Open access	It will be accessible via our website
Deliverable	D4.4 Assessment of feasibility of certification adoption in selected value chains	Lusine Aramyan, Luuk Vissers, Scarlett Wang, (WR – WEcR), Patrick Kohl (CU)	To be uploaded upon acceptance	Research	WEcR, CU	Open access	It will be accessible via our website
Deliverable	D5.1. Summary of project deliverables findings	Laura Väyrynen (ECOS)	To be uploaded upon acceptance	Research	ECOS	Open access	It will be accessible via our website
Deliverable	D5.3 Final policy brief	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED: Iris Vural Gursel (WR); Laura Vayrynen (ECOS) HARMONITOR: Sergio Ugarte (SQ Consult). STAR4BBS: Luana Ladu, Nikola Matovik (Technical University of Berlin).	To be uploaded upon acceptance	Research	WR, ECOS/ SQ Consult /TU Berlin	Open access	It will be accessible via our website

Type	Title	Author(s)	Name of publication/venue & year	Exploitation Interest	Main Partner(s)	Accessibility	Accessibility of data
Deliverable	D5.4. Thematic briefs laying down recommendations to scheme/label owners	Laura Väyrynen (ECOS)	To be uploaded upon acceptance	Research	ECOS	Open access	It will be accessible via our website
Deliverable	D5.5. Thematic briefs to industrial biobased value chain actors	Víctor Fernández Ocamica, Paula de la Sen de la Cruz	To be uploaded upon acceptance	Research	CIRCE	Open access	It will be accessible via our website
Deliverable	D5.6 Thematic briefs to regional bioeconomy actors	Víctor Fernández Ocamica, Paula de la Sen de la Cruz	To be uploaded upon acceptance	Research	CIRCE	Open access	It will be accessible via our website

8. Common Exploitation Strategy for SUSTCERT4BIOBASED's KERs

8.1 Value proposition of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED KERs to the main stakeholders

This section provides a stakeholder mapping for the main target groups that stand to benefit from the project's outcomes. The findings of this analysis are presented in Table 8.

Table 8. Value proposition of the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED KERs to the main stakeholders

KER number	Key Exploitable Result (KER)	Target stakeholder(s)	Main stakeholder needs	Value proposition offered by the KER: how does it cover and deliver the identified needs
KER1	Classification of biological resources and biobased products	All	To get a clear picture on the range of biological resources and biobased products	This classification provided both for biological resources and for biobased products can be used by all stakeholders to understand the diversity and provide a common terminology
KER2	Catalogue of sustainability certification schemes and labels for industrial biobased systems	Industrial actors	To get clear information on the existing schemes/labels	Can be used by industrial actors to get more information on existing schemes and labels for industrial biobased systems
KER3	Identification of the most representative biobased value chains in the EU	Policy makers	To understand the current landscape of biobased value chains	To provide an overview of the identified most prominent biobased value chains in the EU
KER4	Quantification of global trade flows of selected biobased value chains	Policy makers	To understand the trade of (certified)biobased products	Give quantitative data on selected biobased value chains giving a clearer understanding on trade of the biological resources and biobased materials and their level of certification
KER5	BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring tool	Policy makers	To understand the performance of existing schemes/labels	Increase transparency regarding the performance of existing CSLs for biobased systems, including an evaluation of their effectiveness and robustness.

KER number	Key Exploitable Result (KER)	Target stakeholder(s)	Main stakeholder needs	Value proposition offered by the KER: how does it cover and deliver the identified needs
KER6	Results from testing of the BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool on selected certification schemes and labels	Scheme/label owners	Their schemes/labels get more adopted in the market Credibility of their system increases	A tool that can be used by the scheme and label owners to evaluate their schemes and identify their strengths and weakness for improvement.
KER7	Methodology for cost benefit analysis and internalizing of externalities for sustainability certification	Industrial actors	To understand the costs and benefits from adoption of schemes/labels	Methodology to evaluate the cost and benefit from the adoption of certification
KER8	Data collection template for cost and benefit analysis	Industrial actors	To understand the costs and benefits from adoption of schemes/labels	Data collection template to be able to carry out the cost and benefit assessment
KER9	Recommendations to policy makers	Policy makers	Recommendation of how project results can be used in policy measures and EU strategies	A report to be prepared giving recommendations based on project results how they can be used in policy measures and EU strategies
KER10	Recommendations to standards writers, scheme owners and certification bodies	Standardization community, Scheme/label owners	Keep standards up to date with recent discussions and findings	Ensures that standards are current with the latest research and industry practices, supporting innovation and compliance.
KER11	Recommendations to industrial biobased value chain actors	Industrial actors	Recommendation of how project results can be used in industry	Provides recommendations to boost adoption of robust and effective sustainability certification schemes in industry
KER12	Recommendations to regional bioeconomy actors	Regional bioeconomy stakeholders	Improving sustainability of the regions, protecting rural areas	Offers strategies to promote sustainability certification and their integration in the regional bioeconomy strategies.

KER number	Key Exploitable Result (KER)	Target stakeholder(s)	Main stakeholder needs	Value proposition offered by the KER: how does it cover and deliver the identified needs
			Regional value creation	

9. Individual Post-project Exploitation and Valorisation Plans per Partner

9.1 Individual post-project exploitation interests per partner and KER

In projects with multidisciplinary consortia, the type of exploitation interest in a given result often varies among partners. This is due to many reasons, such as differences in each organisation's strategic priorities or the nature of an organisation. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED IPR strategy has considered the main exploitation types that are common in Horizon projects.

Based on the notation presented in section 5.3.1, the table below shows the different types of post-project exploitation interest and strategies/pathways that each partner envisages for each of the project's (Key) Exploitable Results. The partners' exploitation interest may be re-evaluated and modified after the project.

For each result, the partners were asked to provide their exploitation interest, distinguishing between (i) commercial, (ii) internal development (i.e., the result is expected to be used within the project for improving certain processes/products/services in the respective partner's organisation), (iii) research, and (iv) other exploitation pathways.

Table 9. Individual post-project exploitation interests

<p>C(M) - Commercial: Making or improving a product to sell it</p> <p>C(L) - Commercial: Licensing it to third parties</p> <p>C(S) - Commercial: Providing a service, such as consultancy</p> <p>I - Internal (e.g. using the KER to improve products or organizational processes)</p> <p>R - Research (e.g. in new research projects or internal R&D activities)</p> <p>O - Others (please specify)</p>	Classification of biological resources and biobased products	Catalogue of sustainability certification schemes and labels	Identification of the most representative biobased value chains in the EU	Quantification of global trade flows of biobased value chains	BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring system	Results from testing of the BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool on selected certification schemes and labels	Methodology for cost benefit analysis and internalizing of externalities for sustainability certification	Data collection template for cost and benefit analysis	Recommendations to policy makers	Recommendations to standards writers, scheme owners and certification bodies	Recommendations to standards writers, scheme owners and certification bodies	Recommendations to regional bioeconomy actors
	Exploitation interest/strategy	Exploitation interest/strategy	Exploitation interest/strategy	Exploitation interest/strategy	Exploitation interest/strategy	Exploitation interest/strategy	Exploitation interest/strategy	Exploitation interest/strategy	Exploitation interest/strategy	Exploitation interest/strategy	Exploitation interest/strategy	Exploitation interest/strategy
WR	C(S)	C(S)	C(S), I, R	C(S), I, R	C(S), I, R	I, R	C(S), I, R	C(S),I,R	C(S),I	C(S),I	C(S),I	C(S),I
CIRCE	C(S)	C(S)	C(S), I, R	C(S), I, R							C(S),I	C(S),I
WHITE		R							R	R	R	R
ECOS					C(S),I	I			C(S),I	C(S),I	I	I
CU	I	I	I	I	C(S), I	I	I	I,R	I	I		

9.2 Overall valorisation plans per partner

Lastly, this section presents each **project partner's general valorisation plans for the overall results and knowledge** stemming from the entire work performed during the project. Complementing the exploitation plans at the result level, in this section each partner identifies which project assets they are more interested in exploiting and describes, briefly, how they intend to make use of the results generated, and the knowledge gained, throughout their activities in SUSTCERT4BIOBASED. These post-project exploitation plans relate to organisational-level activities and goals. The information is therefore presented separately for each specific consortium partner in the table below:

Table 10. Overall valorisation plans per partner

Individual post-project exploitation plans		
Partner organization name	Project results of major interest	Description
WR	Catalogue of sustainability certification schemes and labels, Methodology for cost-benefit analysis, BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool, Results from testing of the BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool on selected certification schemes and labels	As a research organisation WR will build on the knowledge gained from SUSTCERT4BIOBASED to strengthen the capabilities and know-how and provide improved services to relevant stakeholders and policy makers in follow up projects. This includes increased knowledge and understanding of the sustainability requirements of sustainability certification schemes and labels for industrial biobased systems, and development of the methodology to assess the costs and benefits from adoption of certification that can be further valorized in new projects. Additionally, the experience gained with coordination of the project will provide WR with enhanced capabilities in project management. The expanded network of WR through SUSTCERT4BIOBASED that includes project partners from collaborating sister projects as well as engaged range of stakeholders, will provide WR with future collaboration possibilities in consortium of new European projects on the topic of sustainability of biobased industry.
CIRCE	Classification of biological resources and biobased products, Identification of the most representative biobased value chains in the EU	CIRCE, with its expertise in energy, environmental sustainability, and innovation in biobased industries, will build on the project results to further develop and expand their analytical models for value chain assessments, incorporating social criteria that are often lacking in current datasets. This work will enhance CIRCE's capability to support companies and stakeholders in the biobased sector to adopt more sustainable practices and certification systems. CIRCE plans to apply these methodologies in future projects, such as those aimed at advancing the bioeconomy, supporting the decarbonization of industry, and promoting circular economy principles.

Individual post-project exploitation plans		
Partner organization name	Project results of major interest	Description
WHITE	Project website, Network of Interest, methodologies and deliverables related to IPR, engagement and dissemination	WHITE is a social research SME specialised in consumer behaviour, market analysis, and innovation management in key sectors including Bioeconomy. The company will build on the knowledge derived from SUSTCERT4BIOBASED as well as its results to improve its services, analytic tools and know-how with regard to the EU's bioeconomy sector. More specifically, the expanded network of stakeholders that WR engages through SUSTCERT4BIOBASED—ranging from industry professionals to policymakers and researchers—will be a key asset moving forward. WR plans to leverage this network to build partnerships, open new consulting and business opportunities, and identify prospects for future research funding. Additionally, the project will provide WR with enhanced expertise in IPR management, which the company will utilize to offer more comprehensive services to clients across the bioeconomy and related sectors. The dissemination and engagement experience gained will also be applied to future projects, enhancing WR's capacity to communicate impactful results and create strong collaboration among stakeholders.
ECOS	BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool, Recommendations to standards writers, scheme owners and certification bodies, Review of existing monitoring approaches for schemes and labels	As an environmental NGO working in, among other topics, bioeconomy and biobased products as well as private sustainability certification systems, ECOS will utilise the knowledge gained from SUSTCERT4BIOBASED to further advocate for more environmentally friendly standards, policies, and laws. More specifically, the knowledge and experience gained from developing the BMT will support ECOS' voluntary sustainability standards strategy. In addition, the networks gained from the project, both those of project partners as well as external parties such as certification schemes and labels, will support potential future collaboration regarding funding and Horizon projects, as well as furthering the voluntary sustainability standards strategy of ECOS.
CU	Study of existing biobased certification schemes and labels, BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool	CU will focus on applying the knowledge gained from SUSTCERT4BIOBASED to enhance its sustainability certification services, particularly by studying the effectiveness of existing biobased certification schemes and labels. The Biobased Monitoring Tool (BMT) will be crucial for CU's future endeavours, allowing to offer enhanced sustainability certification services to clients across the agriculture and biobased industries. CU's post-project exploitation will focus on applying the results from the project to develop improved, scalable sustainability certification models for diverse stakeholders in international markets. Furthermore, CU will continue collaborating with other organizations, policymakers, and industries to ensure that the BMT and other developed tools are widely adopted across Europe and beyond.

10. Conclusions

The SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project has created a clear and well-structured approach to managing innovation, intellectual property (IP), exploitation, and sustainability, ensuring that its results are not only well-protected but also positioned for lasting impact. The project has successfully identified, categorized, and developed plans for the future use of its Key Exploitable Results (KERs), making sure that they hold real value for stakeholders in the bio-based sector.

One of the main achievements has been the collaboration with HARMONITOR and STAR4BBS, where joint ownership and exploitation strategies were created. This collaboration is especially significant for the BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool, the project's key result, which the team plans to continue developing and using after the project ends. A Co-ownership Agreement has already been drafted, and discussions about the next steps for exploiting the tool already took place.

To ensure that project results are easily accessible, all public outputs are available via the project's website and Zenodo, pending European Commission approval. The report also details the various IP protection measures and exploitation paths, ensuring that the project's outcomes are legally protected while also being available for commercialization, development, and policy use. The post-project valorization plans emphasize the commitment from all consortium partners to ensure the project's innovations continue benefiting the sector long after the project ends.

Looking to the future, the SUSTCERT4BIOBASED consortium, together with the BIOBASEDCERT Cluster, plans to further spread the project's results and identify new opportunities in future projects. This will help keep the BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool evolving and fully aligned with the needs of the bio-based sector, ensuring the impact of the project continues to grow after its end.

11. Annex

11.1 Annex I – Co-ownership Agreement

**Co-Ownership Agreement for BIOBASEDCERT
cluster Asset**

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED, HARMONITOR, STAR4BBS

22/5/2025

Co-Ownership Agreement for BIOBASEDCERT cluster Asset

This Co-Ownership Agreement ("Agreement") is made and entered into force as of XXX by and between:

On behalf of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project:

- **STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH (WR)** , located at DROEVENDAALSESTEEG 4, WAGENINGEN 6708 PB, Netherlands , from Project SUSTCERT4BIOBASED
- **ENVIRONMENTAL COALITION ON STANDARDS (ECOS)**, located at RUE DU COMMERCE 31, BRUXELLES 1000, Belgium from Project SUSTCERT4BIOBASED

On behalf of HARMONITOR project:

- **UTRECHT UNIVERSITY (UU)**, located at Heidelberglaan 8, 3583 CS Utrecht,the Netherlands from project HARMONITOR

On behalf of STAR4BBS project:

- **Technical University of Berlin (TUB)**, located at [Straße des 17. Juni 135, 10623 Berlin]

(collectively referred to as "Parties").

1. Representation and Authority:

Each Party acknowledges and agrees that it is solely responsible for determining its internal governance and ensuring that the person(s) signing this Agreement on its behalf have the full legal authority to bind all member organizations within their respective consortium, if applicable. By signing this Agreement, each signatory warrants that they are duly authorized to execute this Agreement and that such execution will bind all relevant entities in their consortium, without the need for additional signatures or approvals.

2. Internal Governance Disclaimer:

The Parties agree that no Party to this Agreement, including their consortia, shall bear any responsibility or liability for how another consortium manages its internal decision-making or signatory authorization process. Any disputes arising within a consortium regarding representation, internal governance, or decision-making shall not affect the validity, enforceability, or obligations of this Agreement as executed by the authorized signatory(ies).

3. Non-Interference:

The Parties recognize and respect each consortium's autonomy to organize and manage its internal governance and signatory process without interference or oversight from the other Parties to this Agreement.

Introduction

1.1 The Partners are engaged in the development and maintenance of the below Asset

- BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool (BMT)

Description:

BMT is a tool designed to support policymakers, certification scheme owners, and the biobased industry in evaluating the robustness, comprehensiveness and effectiveness of sustainability certification schemes and labels for industrial biobased systems. 1.2 The purpose of this Agreement is to set forth the terms and conditions for the co-ownership of the cluster's Assets.

Definitions

2.1 BIOBASEDCERT cluster: A collaboration between the below Horizon Europe funded projects:

A. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED : Sustainability Certification for Biobased Systems , 101059785

B. HARMONITOR: Harmonisation and monitoring platform for certification schemes and labels to advance the sustainability of bio-based systems , 101060133

C. STAR4BBS : Sustainability Transition Assessment Rules for Bio-Based Systems, 101060588

2.1 Assets: all Intellectual Property and Results and any other assets developed or acquired during the course of the cluster’s collaboration.

2.2 Confidential Information: Any non-public information related to the Project and its assets.

2.3 Intellectual Property: includes inventions (whether patentable or not), patents, patent applications, trademarks, registered designs, and applications thereof, copyright material including computer software, technical information, and know-how.

2.4 Results: means any (tangible or intangible) output of the project such as data, knowledge, or information — whatever its form or nature, whether it can be protected or not — that was generated in the project, as well as any rights attached to it, including intellectual property rights.

Ownership and Shares

3.1 The Parties agree that all Assets of the cluster shall be co-owned equally by the three consortia, with each consortium holding a one-third (1/3) share of ownership of the BMT and its respective level they developed and were responsible for (system level for STAR4BBS, content level for SUSTCERT4BIOBASED, outcome level for HARMONITOR project). Each consortium’s one-third (1/3) share shall be further divided among the contributing partners of the respective consortium, based on internal decisions regarding the allocation of project shares. Each consortium retains full autonomy to decide internally how their share will be divided among their members, according to the contributions and calculations agreed upon by the consortium partners.

3.2 To provide a clear overview of the ownership structure, Table 1 below illustrates the respective contributions of each co-owning Partner to each Asset, as per the agreements outlined in this Article.

Table 11. Overview of the ownership structure

Asset Name	SUSTCERT4BIOBASED – Content level (1/3 Share)	HARMONITOR – Outcome level (1/3 Share)	STAR4BBS – System level (1/3 Share)
BMT	WFBR (50%) ECOS (50%)	UU (100%)	TUB (100%)

Explanation of ownership calculations:

The division of shares within each consortium was determined based on internal partner decisions (Each consortium used its own methodology to divide its share, considering factors such as technical contributions, resource allocation, and time invested etc.)

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED: The partners agreed to allocate 50% of the consortium’s project share to WFBR and 50% to ECOS, based on their substantial contributions to the development of the BMT.

HARMONITOR: The partners agreed to allocate 100% of the consortium’s project share UU, based on their substantial contributions to the development of the outcome level methodology of the BMT.

STAR4BBS: The partners agreed to allocate 100% of the consortium’s project share to TUB, based on its role as coordinator of the STAR4BBS project and of leader of WP4 devoted to the preparation of the BMT.

Rights and Responsibilities

4.1 Management: The Partners shall jointly manage the Assets. Any significant decisions regarding the management of the Assets must be approved by 2/3 majority of the Partners.

4.2 Use of Assets: The Project Assets shall be made available for use by the public, subject to any terms and conditions agreed upon by the Partners. For models and data, the Partners shall select users’ rights from the catalogue of Creative Commons and select a repository of one of the Partners, that will host such data and models.

4.3 Maintenance: The Partners agree to share based on the division ownership in section 3, in the responsibility and cost of prosecuting Intellectual Property Rights pertaining to the Project Assets and the maintenance of the Intellectual Property Rights and the Assets.

Intellectual Property protection

The Parties that co-own a result may appoint one of them (“Managing Partner”) to oversee the protection, filing and prosecution of the relevant Intellectual Property Right. The Managing Partner may prepare, file, and prosecute applications regarding the Intellectual Property Right of the Asset after consulting with the other Parties in good faith. Any such applications shall be registered in name of all co-owning Partners. The Managing Partner shall keep all patent notices, applications and correspondence filed in connection with any such applications and shall provide copies of such documents to the other Partners on reasonable request.

All costs resulting from the above procedures (including filing, prosecution, and renewal fees) shall be borne by the Partners in proportion to their respective shares of the relevant Result.

Each Partner shall inform the other Partners promptly of any infringement or suspected or threatened infringement of the Result of which it becomes aware, and the Partners shall promptly consult with each other in good faith with a view to reaching agreement on the action to be taken in respect of the infringement in question. A decision on the action must be approved by 2/3 majority of the Partners.

The Table below provides an overview of the IP protection measures foreseen for each of the assets produced by the cluster as agreed by partners at the time of the signature of the current agreement.

	Result	Protection Measure
ER1	BMT (BIOBASEDCERT Monitoring Tool)	Copyright, (CC BY-NC-SA)

Financial Contributions

6.1 The Partners agree that there will be no expectation of income from the Assets at this time.

6.2 Any necessary financial contributions towards the development, maintenance, and protection of the Assets shall be shared based on the division ownership in section 3 by the Partners.

Exploitation

Exploitation for Research Non-Commercial Purposes

Each Partner is entitled to use the results for research non-commercial purposes without compensation to the other parties. However, a 30-day advance notice should be provided to the other parties. This provision includes using the Asset as background in research projects such as HORIZON.

Acknowledgment and Attribution:

Partners utilizing the Results for research purposes must appropriately acknowledge and attribute the Result owners in all related publications, presentations, or other forms of dissemination. The attribution should follow standard academic and scientific practices, including citation of the original work and reference to the Result owners.

Disclaimer and Acknowledgment:

In all publications or presentations, the following acknowledgment should be included:

“This work is part of the BIOBASEDCERT cluster and is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike (CC BY-NC-SA) license. The authors acknowledge the contributions of WFBR, ECOS, UU, and TUB in the development of this asset.”

Public Access and Uploading:

All three consortia will upload the BMT to their respective websites. Additionally, the BMT will be uploaded to Zenodo for wider accessibility and dissemination.

Intentions for continuation:

The following outlines the anticipated continuation and further development of the BMT, based on preliminary discussions with relevant projects and stakeholders. These plans are **indicative in nature and do not represent binding commitments**:

- **HARMONITOR Project:** A PhD student from Utrecht University is expected to take over the further development of the Outcome level, supporting its continued development within an academic framework.
- **STAR4BBS Project:** The project has expressed intentions to further develop the System level of the Tool in a standardization output (e.g. CEN Workshop Agreement). In addition, STAR4BBS is preparing a Web-based version of the BMT Tool, incorporating the current version (date 31.05.2025) of the BMT. This Web-based tool will be hosted until the 31.08.2028 in the STAR4BBS webpage.
- **SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Project:** Through the involvement of the project’s coordinator, who is a member of the Dutch Technical Standards Committee, SUSTCERT4BIOBASED intends to promote the Tool and explore its relevance within the committee’s working group.

These plans reflect current intentions and may evolve based on project priorities, available resources, and emerging opportunities.

Confidentiality

8.1 Neither Partner will for five (5) years after the date of this Agreement disclose to any third party, nor use for any purpose except as expressly permitted by this Agreement, any of the other Partner's Confidential Information.

Neither Partner will be in breach of clause 8.1 to the extent that any information:

- is known to the receiving Partner before its receipt from the other Partner, and not already subject to any obligation of confidentiality to the other Partner;
- is or becomes publicly known without any breach of this Agreement or any other undertaking to keep it confidential;
- has been obtained by the receiving Partner from a third party in circumstances where the receiving Partner has no reason to believe that there has been a breach of an obligation of confidentiality owed to the other Partner;
- has been independently developed by the receiving Partner;
- is disclosed pursuant to the requirement of any law or regulation or the order of any court of competent jurisdiction, and the Partner required to make that disclosure has informed the other, within a reasonable time after being required to make the disclosure, of the requirement to disclose and the information required to be disclosed;
- is approved for release in writing by an authorised representative of the other Partner.

Dispute Resolution

9.1 This Agreement shall be governed by Belgian law.

9.2 In the event of any dispute related to this Agreement, the Partners shall first seek to negotiate and resolve the dispute amicably under principles of good faith.

9.3 If an amicable settlement cannot be reached, the dispute shall be referred to professional mediation in accordance with Belgian arbitration rules.

9.4 Should negotiation or mediation fail to resolve the dispute, legal proceedings shall be submitted to the jurisdiction of the Belgian courts.

Termination and Amendments

10.1 The Agreement will take effect on the Effective Date and (subject to the remaining sub-clauses of this clause 9) will continue in force until the moment on which the Partners jointly decide to abandon the Assets.

10.2 A Partner may terminate this Agreement with immediate effect by giving notice to the other Partners if:

- (a) the other Partner(s) is/are in breach of any provision of this Agreement and (if it is capable of remedy) the breach has not been remedied within sixty (60) days after receipt of written notice specifying the breach and requiring its remedy. Upon termination the share in the Asset owned by the Partner(s) in breach, shall be transferred to the other Partners without cost; or

(b) the other Partner(s) becomes insolvent, or if an order is made or a resolution is passed for its winding up (except voluntarily for the purpose of solvent amalgamation or reconstruction), or if an administrator, administrative receiver or receiver is appointed over the whole or any part of the other Partner's assets, or if the other Partner makes any arrangement with its creditors. Upon termination the share in the Asset owned by the Partner in insolvency, shall be transferred to the other Partners without cost.

9.3 Upon termination regarding a Partner for any reason, the Assets reside fully either with the other Partners, in which case the Partner no longer owning a share of the Assets will not use nor disclose to any third party any information regarding the Assets or this Agreement;

9.4 Upon termination regarding a Partner for any reason, that Partner shall immediately cease to use any confidential information relating to the other Partners, and shall return, or at the request of the disclosing Partners destroy such confidential information without undue delay;

Miscellaneous

11.1 Force Majeure: If the performance by either Partner of any of its obligations under this Agreement (except a payment obligation) is delayed or prevented by circumstances beyond its reasonable control, that Partner will not be in breach of this Agreement because of that delay in performance. However, if the delay in performance is more than 3 months, the other Partner may terminate this Agreement with immediate effect by giving written notice.

11.2 Amendments: Any changes to this Agreement must be made in writing and signed by all Partners.

11.3 Assignment: neither Partner may assign or transfer this Agreement as a whole, or any of its rights or obligations under it, without first obtaining the written consent of the other Partners

11.4 Entire Agreement: This document constitutes the entire Agreement between the Partners regarding the subject matter.

11.5 Severability: If any provision of this Agreement is found to be invalid or unenforceable, the remaining provisions shall continue to be in effect.

11.6 Notices: Any formal notices under this Agreement shall be in writing and delivered to the addresses specified above.

Signature Section

Disclaimer: This co-ownership agreement is currently a draft and remains subject to ongoing legal review. Final terms are pending verification and approval by the respective legal and compliance departments of the involved parties. No clause or condition herein should be considered legally binding until the final version is executed by all parties.

IN WITNESS WHEREOF, the Partners hereto have executed this Co-Ownership Agreement as of the Effective Date.

On behalf of SUSTCERT4BIOBASED project:

STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH

Iris Vural Gursel

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED Coordinator

Signature: _____

ENVIRONMENTAL COALITION ON STANDARDS

[Name]

[Position]

Signature: _____

On behalf of HARMONITOR project:

UTRECHT UNIVERSITY

[Name]

[Position]

Signature: _____

On behalf of STAR4BBS project:

Technical University of Berlin

Dr. Luana Ladu,

Coordinator of the STAR4BBS project

Signature: _____

Dr. Elke Gehweiler

Head of EU Office

Signature: _____

12. References

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- WIPO Intellectual Property Handbook (2008). Policy, Law and Use. Chapter 2: Fields of Intellectual Property Protection.

About SUSTCERT4BIOBASED

SUSTCERT4BIOBASED is an EU funded (Horizon Europe) project aiming at defining and promoting the adoption of effective and robust sustainability certification schemes and business-to-business labels for industrial biobased systems to support tracing the sustainability (environmental, social, economic) of biobased products along the value chains and trades within the EU and globally for responsible production and consumption. This objective is realised by the development of a monitoring system, mapping of the current situation in global trade flows of biological resources and biobased products, and feasibility assessment from the adoption of certification schemes and labels considering actual economic as well as internalized environmental and social costs and benefits. The results of the project are leveraged to provide recommendations to four key target groups: policy makers, sustainability system community, industrial biobased value chain actors, and regional bioeconomy stakeholders. These ambitions are addressed by a strong, well-balanced, and multi-disciplinary consortium comprised of 5 complementary partners. SUSTCERT4BIOBASED thereby supports the development of harmonized system requirements, continuous improvement of sustainability certification schemes and labels and contributes towards establishing a circular, climate-neutral, and sustainable biobased industry.

PARTNERS

Stichting Wageningen Research (WR)
www.wur.nl

Fundacion Circe Centro de Investigacion de Recursos y Consumos Energeticos (CIRCE)
www.fcirce.es

White Research SRL (WHITE)
white-research.eu

Environmental Coalition on Standards (ECOS)
www.ecostandard.org

Control Union Certifications Germany GmbH (CU)
www.controlunion-germany.com

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